

The Constitution of the European Union

“In Varietate Concordia”

United in Diversity

The Constitution of the European Union

“In Varietate Concordia” (Latin)

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Long live the European Union!

We, the peoples of Europe, unite for a freer,
happier, richer, equal, peaceful and more secure
future!

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Preamble

These laws were written to represent Europe's different states and cultures, which, until the 20th century, fought each other bloodily. They have been written so that the friction can disappear, and these states can live happily together. Forming a peaceful and perfect union based on solidarity and respecting the sovereignty and cultural heritage of each Member State.

INSPIRED by the cultural, religious, and humanist inheritance of Europe, from which have developed the universal values of the inviolable and inalienable rights of the human person, freedom, democracy, equality, and the rule of law.

BELIEVING that Europe, reunited after bitter experiences, intends to continue along the path of civilisation, progress, and prosperity, for the good of all its inhabitants, including the weakest and most deprived; that it wishes to remain a continent open to culture, learning, and social progress; and that it wishes to deepen the democratic and transparent nature of its public life and to strive for peace, justice and solidarity throughout the world.

CONVINCED that, while remaining proud of their own national identities and history, the peoples of Europe are determined to transcend their former divisions and, united ever more closely, to forge a common destiny.

HEREBY DECLARE that this Constitution shall form the basic law of all Member States of the European Union, and the laws of all Member States shall comply with the laws laid down in this Constitution of the European Union. These Member States at present are Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, and Sweden. If the European Union is joined by a new state, the new Member State's laws must also comply with the Constitution of the European Union.

General provisions

Art. 1 The European Union

1. The people and states of Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, and Sweden form the European Union.
2. The European Union is a free, democratic, and social confederation of sovereign member states based on solidarity.
3. All state authority is derived from the people. The people shall exercise it through elections, other votes, and specific legislative, executive, judicial, media, and educational bodies.

Art. 2 Aim of the European Union

1. The European Union shall protect the liberty and rights of the people and safeguard the independence and security of Europe.
2. It shall promote the common welfare, sustainable development, internal cohesion, and cultural diversity of the Union.
3. It will ensure the greatest possible equality of opportunity among its citizens.
4. It is committed to the long-term preservation of natural resources and a just and peaceful international order.

Art. 3 Symbols

1. The Union's official name is the "European Union".
2. The Union's official motto is "In Varietate Concordia" (Latin).
3. The European flag symbolises both the European Union and, more broadly, the identity and unity of Europe. It features a circle of 12 gold stars on a blue background. They represent the ideals of unity, solidarity, and harmony among the peoples of Europe.
4. The hymn of the European Union is the "Ode of Joy" from Ludwig van Beethoven's "Ninth Symphony". There are no words to the anthem; it consists of Beethoven's music only. The anthem expresses the European ideals of freedom, peace, solidarity, and unity.
5. Europe Day, celebrated on May 9th, shall be the only national holiday that is celebrated coordinately throughout the European Union in each Member State.

Art. 4 Languages

1. All official languages of the Member States of the European Union are the official languages of the European Union. This at present includes Bulgarian, Croatian, Czech, Danish, Dutch, English, Estonian, Finnish, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Irish, Italian, Latvian, Lithuanian, Maltese, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, Slovak, Slovene, Spanish, and Swedish. If the European Union is joined by a new State, its language will also become the official language of the European Union.

Art. 5 Democratic values

1. The European Union shall be based on consensus and solidarity as well as the common democratic values respected by each Member State; these democratic values shall be followed by all the Member States of the European Union.
2. All Member States of the European Union must have free elections, democratic decision-making, freedom of speech, equality before the law, and social justice.

Art. 6 Rule of Law

1. All Member States of the European Union must be governed by the rule of law.
2. All activities of the European Union and its Member States are based on and limited by law.
3. State activities must be conducted in the public interest and be proportionate to the ends sought.
4. State institutions and private persons shall act in good faith.
5. The European Union and the Member States shall respect international law.

Basic Rights

Dignity

Art. 7 Human dignity

1. Human dignity, as the basis of European society, shall be inviolable. To respect and protect it shall be the duty of all state authorities.
2. The European people therefore acknowledge inviolable and inalienable human rights as the basis of every community and of peace and justice in the world.
3. The Basic Rights shall bind the legislature, the executive, and the judiciary as directly applicable law.

Art. 8 Right to life

1. Every person has the right to live. The death penalty shall be prohibited.
2. Torture and any other form of cruel, inhuman, or degrading treatment or punishment are prohibited in the European Union.
3. The life sentence is prohibited in the European Union.

Art. 9 Right to the integrity of the person

1. Everyone has the right to respect for his or her physical and mental integrity.
2. In the fields of medicine and biology, the following must be respected in particular:
 - (a) The free and informed consent of the person concerned, according to the procedures laid down by law.
 - (b) The prohibition of eugenic practices, in particular those aiming at the selection of persons.
 - (c) The prohibition on making the human body and its parts a source of financial gain.
 - (d) The prohibition of reproductive cloning of human beings.

Art. 10 Prohibition of slavery and forced labour

1. No one shall be held in slavery or servitude.
2. No one shall be required to perform forced or compulsory labour.

3. Human trafficking is prohibited.

Art. 11 Defence of Minorities

1. In all Member States of the European Union, ethnic, religious, or linguistic minorities or persons belonging to such minorities shall not be denied the right, in community with the other members of their group, to enjoy their own culture, to profess and practice their religion, or to use their language.

Freedoms

Art. 12 Personal freedoms

1. All citizens of the European Union have the right to free development of their personality insofar as they do not violate the rights of others or offend against the constitutional order or the moral law. They shall have the right to life and physical integrity. The freedom of the person shall be inviolable. These rights may be interfered with only pursuant to a law.

Art. 13 Freedom of expression, information and of the media

1. All European Union citizens have the right to express their opinions freely through speech, writing, and pictures and inform themselves without hindrance through independent, freely accessible sources. The freedom of the press, broadcasting, and reporting must be guaranteed. There can be no censorship. These rights shall find their limits in the provisions of general laws, in provisions for the protection of young persons, and in the right to personal honour.

Art. 14 Academic freedom

1. All European Union citizens have the right to do research and teach. The freedom of teaching shall not release any person from allegiance to the Constitution.

Art. 15 Freedom of artistic expression

1. Freedom of artistic expression is guaranteed.

Art. 16 Freedom of assembly

1. All European Union citizens have the right to assemble peacefully and unarmed without permission. This right may be restricted by or pursuant to a law. In case of meetings

held in public places, previous notice shall be given to the authorities, who may prohibit them only for proven reasons of security or public safety.

Art. 17 Freedom of religion and conscience

1. All European Union citizens have the freedom to choose their religion and practice it; this shall be guaranteed.
2. All European Union citizens have the freedom to choose their philosophical convictions and to profess them alone or in community with others.
3. Every person has the right to join or to belong to a religious community and to follow religious teachings.
4. No person may be forced to join or belong to a religious community, participate in a religious act, or follow religious teachings.
5. No religion or philosophical conviction shall take precedence over this constitution or the law.
6. Religion shall remain a private affair of citizens.

Art. 18 Freedom of association

1. All European Union citizens have the freedom to associate or form societies. However, societies and associations that contravene the criminal laws or the constitution shall be prohibited.

Art. 19 Freedom of occupation

1. All European Union citizens have the freedom to choose their occupation or profession. All citizens have the right to choose their workplace. Forced labour and slavery are illegal throughout the European Union.

Art. 20 Freedom of movement

1. All European Union citizens have the freedom of movement throughout the territory of the European Union. This freedom may only be restricted in the case of an imminent danger to the people or their democratic governance. (For instance: to prevent crime, to combat an epidemic, or to respond to a Natural disaster.) There can be no restriction due to political reasons.
2. All European Union citizens have the right to leave the territory of the European Union and return to it, notwithstanding any legal obligations.

Art. 21 Freedom of residence

1. European Union citizens have the right to establish their residence anywhere in the territory of the European Union.

Art. 22 Family

1. Marriage and family enjoy special protection from the European Union.
2. The care and upbringing of children is the right of all married couples. It is the state's duty to help them.
3. Children may be separated from their families against the will of their parents or guardians only pursuant to a law, and only if the parents or guardians fail in their duties or the children are otherwise in danger of serious neglect.
4. Children born outside of marriage shall be provided by legislation with the same opportunities for physical and mental development and their position in society as are enjoyed by those born within marriage.
5. Any couple has the right to adopt children.
6. Parents must be protected in the entire European Union.

Art. 23 Privacy

1. The privacy of a person's private and family life, home, correspondence, telecommunications, post, and internet usage shall be inviolable.
2. Every person has the right to be protected against the misuse of their data.
3. Restrictions can only happen according to law and if they serve the Constitution and the free democratic basis. It can only happen if a court so judges.
4. If a restriction does happen, a court must check the circumstances and judge whether it was legal or not.
5. If an illegal restriction does happen, the authorities who ordered it must be punished by the court.

Art. 24 School

1. All children in the European Union have the right to free education.
2. Parents or guardians have the right to decide whether their children should receive religious instruction.
3. The establishment of private schools is allowed. However, if they serve as an alternative to national schools, they must collaborate with local rules.
4. Parents or guardians have the right to decide if their children should become private students.
5. Private students must take grading exams so that the school authorities see they are being properly taught at home.

Art. 25 Inviolability of the home

1. A home or private property is inviolable.
2. Searches may be authorised only by a judge or, when time is of the essence, by other authorities designated by the laws and may be carried out only in the manner therein prescribed.
3. If particular facts justifying the suspicion that any person has committed an especially serious crime specifically defined by law, technical means of acoustical surveillance of any home in which the suspect is supposedly staying may be employed pursuant to a judicial order for the purpose of prosecuting the offence, provided that alternative methods of investigating the matter would be disproportionately difficult or unproductive. The authorisation shall be for a limited time. The order shall be issued by a panel composed of three judges. When time is of the essence, it may also be issued by a single judge.
4. To avert acute dangers to public safety, especially dangers to life or to the public, technical means of surveillance of the home may be employed only pursuant to judicial order. When time is of the essence, such measures may also be ordered by other authorities designated by a law; a judicial decision shall subsequently be obtained without delay.
5. Interference and restrictions shall otherwise only be permissible to avert a danger to the public or to the life of an individual or, pursuant to a law, to confront an acute danger to public safety and order, in particular, to relieve an accommodation shortage, to combat the danger of an epidemic or to protect young persons at risk.

Art. 26 Guarantee of ownership

1. Everyone has the right to own, use, dispose of, and bequeath his or her lawfully acquired possessions. No one may be deprived of his or her possessions, except in the public interest and in the cases and under the conditions provided for by law, subject to fair compensation being paid in good time for their loss. The use of property may be regulated by law insofar as is necessary for the general interest.
2. Intellectual property shall be protected.
3. The socialisation of property and any restriction on ownership that is equivalent to socialisation shall be fully compensated.

Art. 27 Inheritance

1. Property and the right of inheritance shall be guaranteed by all European Union Member States. Their content and limits shall be defined by the laws.
2. Property entails obligations in all European Union Member States. Its use shall also serve the public good.
3. Expropriation shall only be permissible for the public good. It may only be ordered by or pursuant to a law that determines the nature and extent of compensation. Such compensation shall be determined by establishing an equitable balance between the public interest and the interests of those affected. In case of dispute concerning the amount of compensation, recourse may be had to the ordinary courts.

Art. 28 Right of asylum

1. Any person persecuted on political grounds shall have the right to seek asylum.
2. Paragraph (1) of this Article may not be invoked by a person who enters the territory of the European Union from another third state in which application of the Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees and the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms is assured. The states outside the European Union to which the conditions referred to in the first sentence of this paragraph apply shall be specified by law. In the cases specified in the first sentence of this paragraph, measures to terminate an applicant's stay may be implemented without regard to any legal challenge that may have been instituted against them.
3. By law, states may be specified in which, based on their laws, enforcement practices, and general political conditions, it can be safely concluded that neither political persecution nor inhuman or degrading punishment or treatment exists. It shall be presumed that a

foreigner from such a state is not persecuted, unless he presents evidence justifying the conclusion that, contrary to this presumption, he is persecuted on political grounds.

4. In the cases specified by paragraph (3) of this Article and in other cases that are plainly unfounded or considered to be plainly unfounded, the implementation of measures to terminate an applicant's stay may be suspended by a court only if serious doubts exist as to their legality; the scope of review may be limited, and tardy objections may be disregarded. Details shall be determined by law.
5. Refugees granted asylum in the European Union shall be distributed among the Member States based on their ability to accommodate them, aligned with each Member State's population, financial situation and capacity to integrate. Member States may voluntarily choose to grant asylum to a greater proportion of refugees than so assigned them. Further details shall be determined by law.

Art. 29 Ban on covering the face

1. No person may cover their face in public spaces or in places that are accessible to the public or where services are offered to anyone wishing to partake of them; the ban does not apply to places of worship.
2. No person may force another person to cover their face on the grounds of their sex.
3. The law shall provide for exceptions. These may only be justified on the grounds of health, safety, weather conditions, or local custom.

Art. 30 Digital rights

1. Everyone has the right to access, use, create, and publish digital media, and the right to access the computers, electronic devices, and telecommunications networks necessary to exercise them.
2. There can be no censorship of the Internet; websites and social networks cannot be blocked or censored.
3. All European Union citizens must have control over who stores their personal data.
4. All European Union citizens have the right to anonymity and encryption of their communications.
5. All European Union citizens have the right to remove private information from Internet searches, databases, and directories.

6. All European Union minors must be protected on the Internet, and companies must provide the means to guarantee safe access without infringing the rights of children.
7. Intellectual property must be defended. Authors must be guaranteed recognition of their artistic or literary work and the right to be remunerated for its use while guaranteeing free access to works that are already in the public domain.

Art. 31 Extradition to a foreign state

1. No citizen of the European Union may be extradited to a foreign state, except under conditions prescribed by an international treaty and pursuant to a procedure provided by such treaty and by law. Extraditions are decided by the European Parliament. Any person who is subject to an extradition order has the right to challenge this order in a court of a Member State of the European Union or the European Court of Justice.

Equality

Art. 32 Equality before the law

1. All European Union citizens are equal before the law; there shall be no class distinctions.
2. No person may be discriminated against, in particular on grounds of origin, race, gender, age, language, social position, way of life, religious, ideological, or political convictions, or because of a physical, mental, or psychological disability.
3. Men and women have equal rights. The law shall ensure their equality, both in law and in practice, most particularly in the family, in education, and in the workplace. Men and women have the right to equal pay for work of equal value.
4. The law shall provide for the elimination of inequalities that affect persons with disabilities.

Art. 33 The rights of the child

1. Children shall have the right to such protection and care as is necessary for their well-being. They may express their views freely. Such views shall be taken into consideration on matters which concern them in accordance with their age and maturity.
2. In all actions relating to children, whether taken by public authorities or private institutions, the child's best interests must be a primary consideration.
3. Every child shall have the right to education.

4. Every child shall have the right to maintain on a regular basis a personal relationship and direct contact with both his or her parents unless that is contrary to his or her interests.

Art. 34 The rights of the elderly

1. The European Union recognises and respects the rights of the elderly to lead a life of dignity and independence and to participate in social and cultural life.

Art. 35 Integration of persons with disabilities

1. The European Union recognises and respects the right of persons with disabilities to benefit from measures designed to ensure their independence, social and occupational integration, and participation in the life of the community.

Art. 36 Equality between women and men

1. Equality between women and men must be ensured in all areas, including employment, work, and pay.
2. In the pursuit of their equality, no action or measure shall be taken that violates the principle of equal opportunity.

Social Rights

Art. 37 Social security and social assistance

1. The European Union recognises and respects the entitlement to social security benefits and social services providing protection in cases such as maternity, illness, industrial accidents, dependency or old age, and the case of loss of employment, in accordance with the rules laid down by European Union law and Member State laws and practices.
2. Everyone residing and moving legally within the European Union is entitled to social security benefits and social advantages in accordance with European Union law and Member State laws and practices.
3. To combat social exclusion and poverty, the European Union recognises and respects the right to social and housing assistance to ensure a decent existence for all those who lack sufficient resources, in accordance with the rules laid down by European Union law and Member State laws and practices.

Art. 38 Workers' welfare support

1. Every citizen unable to work and without the necessary means of subsistence is entitled to welfare support.
2. Workers have the right to be assured adequate means for their needs and necessities in the case of accidents, illness, disability, old age, and involuntary unemployment.
3. Disabled and handicapped persons are entitled to receive education and vocational training.
4. Responsibilities under this Article are entrusted to entities and institutions established by or supported by each Member State.
5. Private-sector assistance may be freely provided.

Art. 39 Health care

1. Everyone has the right of access to preventive health care and the right to benefit from medical treatment under the conditions established by Member States' laws and practices. A high level of human health protection shall be ensured in the definition and implementation of all the European Union's policies and activities.

Art. 40 Consumer protection

1. The European Union policies shall ensure a high level of consumer protection.

Economic Rights**Art. 41 Workers' rights**

1. Workers have the right to remuneration commensurate with the quantity and quality of their work and, in any case, sufficient to ensure them and their families a free and dignified existence.
2. Maximum daily working hours shall be established by law.
3. Workers have the right to two weekly rest days and paid annual holidays. No employer can refuse this right, and no employee can waive this right.

Art. 42 Right to form professional associations

1. Employees, employers, and their organisations have the right to join together to protect their interests, to form associations, and to join or not to join such associations.
2. Disputes must, wherever possible, be resolved through negotiation or mediation.
3. Strikes and lockouts are permitted if they relate to employment relations and if they do not contravene any requirements to preserve peaceful employment relations or to conduct conciliation proceedings.
4. The law may prohibit certain categories of persons from taking strike action.

Art. 43 Right to form trade unions

1. Trade unions may be freely established.
2. No obligations may be imposed on trade unions other than registration at local or central offices, according to the provisions of the law.
3. A condition for registration is that the statutes of the trade unions establish their internal organisation on a democratic basis.
4. Registered trade unions are legal persons. They may, through a unified representation that is proportional to their membership, enter into collective labour agreements that have a mandatory effect for all persons belonging to the categories referred to in the agreement.

Art. 44 Workers' right to information and consultation within the undertaking

1. Workers or their representatives must, at the appropriate levels, be guaranteed information and consultation in good time in the cases and under the conditions provided for by European Union law and Member State laws and practices.

Art. 45 Right of collective bargaining and strike action

1. Workers and employers, or their respective organisations, have, in accordance with European Union law and Member State laws and practices, the right to negotiate and conclude collective agreements at the appropriate levels and, in cases of conflicts of interest, to take collective action to defend their interests, including strike action.

Art. 46 Right to access placement services

1. Everyone has the right to access a free placement service.

Art. 47 Protection in the event of unjustified dismissal

1. Every worker has the right to protection against unjustified dismissal under European Union law and Member State laws and practices.

Art. 48 Prohibition of child labour and protection of young people at work

1. The employment of children is prohibited. The minimum age of admission to employment may not be lower than the minimum school-leaving age, without prejudice to such rules as may be more favourable to young people and except for limited derogations.
2. Young people admitted to work must have working conditions appropriate to their age and be protected against economic exploitation and any work likely to harm their safety, health, or physical, mental, moral, or social development or to interfere with their education.

Art. 49 Family and professional life

1. The family shall enjoy legal, economic, and social protection.
2. To reconcile family and professional life, everyone shall have the right to protection from dismissal for a reason connected with maternity and the right to paid maternity leave and parental leave following the birth or adoption of a child.

Art. 50 Freedom to conduct a business

1. The freedom to conduct a business in accordance with European Union law and the Member States' laws and practices is recognised.

Art. 51 Socialisation

1. All European Union Member States shall have the right to socialise land, natural resources, and means of production so as they be transferred to public ownership or other forms of public enterprise by a law that determines the nature and extent of compensation. Concerning such compensation, the third and fourth sentences of paragraph (3) of Article 27 shall apply.

Citizenship and Citizens Rights

Art. 52 Citizenship

1. All nationals of any Member State of the European Union are citizens of the European Union. European Union citizenship shall be additional to Member State nationality and not replace it.
2. Any national of one of the Member States may, after working or residing at least five consecutive years in another Member State, become the national of that Member State, but only if he speaks the official language of the Member State.
3. Any non-European Union national working and residing for ten consecutive years in a Member State, and speaking the official language of the Member State, may become a national of that Member State.
4. No European Union citizen may be deprived of their European Union citizenship.

Art. 53 Right to vote

1. All European Union citizens who have attained the voting age in the Member State in which they reside have the right to vote in that Member State's municipal elections and European Parliament elections under the same conditions as nationals of that Member State.
2. All European Union citizens who have attained the voting age of the Member State of which they are nationals shall have the right to vote in that Member State's national elections.
3. The vote must be personal and equal, free, and secret. The exercise thereof is a civic duty.
4. The right to vote cannot be restricted except for civil incapacity or as a consequence of an irrevocable penal sentence or in cases of moral unworthiness as laid down by law.

Art. 54 Right to stand as a candidate in elections

1. Every citizen of the European Union has the right to stand as a candidate at elections to the European Parliament in the Member State in which he or she resides, under the same conditions as nationals of that Member State.
2. Every citizen of the European Union has the right to stand as a candidate at the national elections of the Member State of which he is a national.

3. Every citizen of the European Union has the right to stand as a candidate at municipal elections in the Member State in which he or she resides under the same conditions as nationals of that Member State.

Art. 55 Right to good administration

1. Every person has the right to have his or her affairs handled impartially, fairly, and within a reasonable time by the institutions, bodies, offices, and agencies of the European Union and its Member States.
2. This right includes:
 - (a) The right of every person to be heard before any individual measure which would affect him or her adversely is taken.
 - (b) The right of every person to have access to his or her file, while respecting the legitimate interests of confidentiality and professional and business secrecy.
 - (c) The obligation of the administration to give reasons for its decisions.
3. Every person has the right to have the European Union or its Member State make good any damage caused by its institutions or by its servants in the performance of their duties, in accordance with the general principles common to the laws of the Member States.
4. Every person may write to the institutions of the European Union in one of the official languages of the European Union and must have an answer in the same language.

Art. 56 Right of access to documents

1. Any citizen of the European Union and any natural or legal person residing or having its registered office in a Member State has a right of access to documents of the institutions, bodies, offices, and agencies of the European Union and its Member States, whatever their medium.

Art. 57 Right to refer to the European Ombudsman

1. Any citizen of the European Union and any natural or legal person residing or having its registered office in a Member State has the right to refer to the European Ombudsman cases of maladministration in the activities of the institutions, bodies, offices, or agencies of the European Union and its Member States, except for the Court of Justice of the European Union and the Court of Justice of the Member States acting in their judicial role.

Art. 58 Right to petition

1. Every person has the right, without prejudice, to petition the authorities.
2. The authorities must acknowledge receipt of such petitions.

Art. 59 Political rights

1. Political rights are guaranteed.
2. The guarantee of political rights protects the freedom of the citizen to form an opinion and to give genuine expression to his or her will.

Art. 60 Right to form a political party

1. Any European Union citizen has the right to freely establish political parties to contribute to determining national or European policies through democratic processes.
2. Political parties shall participate in the formation of the political will of the people. Their internal organisation shall comply with democratic principles. They shall publicly account for the origin and use of their funds and their assets.
3. Parties which, by their aims or the conduct of their supporters, seek to impair or eliminate the free democratic basic order or to endanger the existence of the European Union are unconstitutional.
4. Parties whose aims or the conduct of their supporters are such as to impair or eliminate the free democratic basic order or to endanger the existence of the European Union shall be excluded from state funding. If such an exclusion is established, tax advantages for such parties and contributions to such parties shall also cease to apply. Furthermore, such parties may be excluded from participating in any election.
5. The European Court of Justice shall decide on the question of unconstitutionality according to paragraph 3 and on the exclusion from state funding according to paragraph 4.
6. The European Congress shall legislate on further details.

Art. 61 Diplomatic and consular protection

1. Every citizen of the European Union shall, in the territory of a third country in which the Member State of which he or she is a national is not represented, be entitled to protection by the diplomatic or consular authorities of any Member State, on the same conditions as the nationals of that Member State.

Art. 62 Military service

1. All European Union citizens who have attained the age of eighteen may be called upon to serve in the European Union Armed Forces, in Frontex the European Union's border police, in the civil defence organisations of the European Union, or in any alternative service.
2. Any person who, on grounds of conscience, refuses to render military service involving the use of arms may be required to perform alternative service. The duration of alternative service shall not exceed that of military service. Details shall be regulated by a law, which shall not interfere with the freedom to decide in accordance with the dictates of conscience and which shall also provide for the possibility of alternative service not connected with units of the European Union Armed Forces or the European Union's border police Frontex.
3. Persons liable to compulsory military service who are not called upon to render service according to paragraph (1) or (2) of this Article may, when a state of defence is in effect, be assigned by or pursuant to a law to employment involving civilian services for defence purposes, including the protection of the civilian population; they may be assigned to public employment only for the purpose of discharging police functions or such other sovereign functions of public administration as can be discharged only by persons employed in the public service. The employment contemplated by the first sentence of this paragraph may include services within the European Union Armed Forces, in the provision of military supplies or with public administrative authorities; employment assignments connected with supplying and servicing the civilian population shall be permissible only to meet their basic requirements or to guarantee their safety.
4. If, during a state of defence, the need for civilian services in the civilian health system or stationary military hospitals cannot be met voluntarily, persons liable to compulsory military service who are not called upon to render service according to paragraph (1), (2) or (3) of this Article may, when a state of defence is in effect, be assigned by or pursuant to law to render such services.
5. If, during a state of defence, the need for workers in the areas specified in the second sentence of paragraph (3) of this Article cannot be met voluntarily, the right of European Union citizens to abandon their occupation or place of employment may be restricted by or according to law to meet this need.
6. Before calling upon its citizens, the European Union shall aim to fill its vacant military positions voluntarily.

Justice

Art. 63 Guarantee of access to the courts

1. In a legal dispute, every person has the right to have their case determined by a judicial authority.
2. Every person has the right to equal and fair treatment in judicial and administrative proceedings and to have their case decided within a reasonable time.
3. Each party to a case has the right to be heard.
4. Any person who does not have sufficient means has the right to free legal advice and assistance unless their case appears to have no prospect of success. If it is necessary to safeguard their rights, they also have the right to free legal representation in court.

Art. 64 Judicial proceedings

1. Any person whose case falls to be judicially decided has the right to have their case heard by a legally constituted, competent, independent, and impartial court. Occasional courts are prohibited.
2. Unless otherwise provided by law, any person against whom civil proceedings have been raised has the right to have their case decided by a court within the jurisdiction in which they reside.
3. Unless the law provides otherwise, court hearings and the delivery of judgements shall be in public.

Art. 65 Criminal proceedings

1. Every person is presumed innocent until they have been found guilty by a legally enforceable judgement.
2. Every accused person has the right to be notified as quickly and comprehensively as possible of the charge brought against them. They must be given the opportunity to assert their rights to a proper defence.
3. Every convicted person has the right to have their conviction reviewed by a higher court, except for cases in which the European Court of Justice sits at first instance.

Art. 66 Principles of legality and proportionality of criminal offences and penalties

1. No one shall be held guilty of any criminal offence on account of any act or omission which did not constitute a criminal offence under national law or international law at the time when it was committed. Nor shall a heavier penalty be imposed than the one that was applicable at the time the criminal offence was committed. If, subsequent to the commission of a criminal offence, the law provides for a lighter penalty, that penalty shall be applicable.
2. This Article shall not prejudice the trial and punishment of any person for any act or omission which, at the time when it was committed, was criminal according to the general principles recognised by the community of nations.
3. The severity of penalties must not be disproportionate to the criminal offence.

Art. 67 Right not to be tried or punished twice in criminal proceedings for the same criminal offence

1. No one shall be liable to be tried or punished again in criminal proceedings for an offence for which he or she has already been finally acquitted or convicted within the European Union in accordance with the law.

Art. 68 Deprivation of liberty

1. No person may be deprived of their liberty other than in the circumstances and the manner provided for by the law.
2. Any person deprived of his liberty has the right to be notified without delay and in a language he can understand, the reasons for his detention and his rights. He must be given the opportunity to exercise his rights, in particular, the right to have his next of kin informed.
3. Any person in pre-trial detention has the right to be brought before a court without delay. The court decides whether the person must remain in detention or be released. Any person in pre-trial detention has the right to have their case decided within a reasonable time.
4. Any person who has been deprived of their liberty by a body other than a court has the right to have recourse to a court at any time. The court shall decide as quickly as possible on the legality of their detention.

Art. 69 Forfeiture

1. Whoever abuses the freedom of expression (Article 13), in particular the freedom of the press (Article 13), the freedom of teaching (Article 14), the freedom of assembly (Article 16), the freedom of association (Article 18), the privacy of correspondence, posts and telecommunications (Article 23), the rights of property (Article 26) or the right of asylum (Article 28) in order to combat the free democratic basic order shall forfeit these basic rights. This forfeiture and its extent shall be declared by the European Court of Justice.
2. Whoever abuses a basic right that has not been restricted by legal power in order to combat the free democratic basic order shall forfeit this basic right. This forfeiture and its extent shall be declared by the European Court of Justice.

Application and Restriction of the Basic rights

Art. 70 Upholding of Basic rights

1. Basic rights must be upheld throughout the legal system of the European Union and its Member States.
2. Whoever acts on behalf of the European Union or its Member States institutions, bodies, offices, and agencies is bound by the basic rights and is under a duty to contribute to their implementation.
3. The authorities shall ensure that the basic rights, where appropriate, apply to relationships among private persons.

Art. 71 Restriction of the Basic rights

1. Restrictions on the basic rights must have a legal basis. Any restriction must be approved by two-thirds of the Members of the European Parliament, and a double-qualified majority of the Members of the European Council. It must then also be approved by the European Court of Justice. Such a law must apply generally and not merely to a single case. The foregoing does not apply in cases of serious and immediate danger where no other course of action is possible.
2. Restrictions on basic rights must be justified in the public interest or for the protection of the basic rights of others.
3. The restriction of the basic rights can only happen for a pre-agreed time. This time shall be determined by the European Parliament, and at the end of such time, the restriction on basic rights will also end.

4. Any restrictions on the basic rights must be proportionate.
5. The essence of basic rights is sacred.

Art. 72 Prohibition of abuse of rights

1. None of these basic rights shall be interpreted as implying any right to engage in any activity or to perform any act aimed at the destruction of any of the rights and freedoms recognised in this Constitution or at their limitation to a greater extent than is provided for herein.

Social objectives

Art. 73 Social Objectives of the European Union and its Member States

1. The European Union and its Member States shall, as a complement to personal responsibility and private initiative, endeavour to ensure that:
 - (a) Every citizen has access to the health care that they require.
 - (b) Families are protected and encouraged as communities of adults and children.
 - (c) Every citizen who is fit to work can earn their living by working under fair conditions.
 - (d) Any citizen seeking accommodation for themselves and their family can find suitable accommodation on reasonable terms.
 - (e) All children and young people, as well as persons of employable age, can obtain an education and undergo basic and advanced training in accordance with their abilities.
 - (f) All children and young people are encouraged to develop into independent and socially responsible people and are supported in their social, cultural, and political integration.
2. The European Union and its Member States shall endeavour to ensure that every person is protected against the economic consequences of old age, invalidity, illness, accident, unemployment, maternity, being orphaned, and being widowed.
3. They shall endeavour to achieve these social objectives within the scope of their constitutional powers and the resources available to them.
4. No direct right to state benefits may be established based on these social objectives.

Legislative powers

Art. 74 The legislative powers of the European Union

1. All legislative powers herein granted shall be vested in the citizens of the European Union, the legislature of the Member States and the European Congress, which shall consist of the European Parliament and the European Council. The European Parliament shall represent Europe as a whole, while the European Council shall represent the wishes of each Member State.

Art. 75 The European Parliament

1. The European Parliament shall be composed of 751 Members chosen every fifth year by the people of the European Union via universal suffrage in a personal, free, equal, and secret vote.
2. No person shall be a Member of the European Parliament who shall not have attained the Age of eighteen years and been five years a citizen of the European Union.
3. The seats in the European Parliament shall be distributed as follows:
 - (a) Each Member State shall have at least two seats in the European Parliament.
 - (b) Fifty of the seven hundred and fifty-one seats in the European Parliament shall be allocated through a Europe-wide party list based on whole shares and highest remainders.
 - (c) Of the remaining seven hundred and one seats, two seats shall be allocated directly to each Member State.
 - (d) The distribution of the remaining seats among the Member States shall be obtained by dividing the number of inhabitants of the European Union, according to the most recent general census of the population, by seven hundred and one minus the seats obtained directly and by distributing the seats in proportion to the population of each Member State, based on whole shares and highest remainders.
4. A census must be held one year before every second election in all Member States so that the correct number of Members can be calculated.
5. When a vacancy happens in the representation from any Member State, the Government thereof shall issue Writs of Election to fill such a vacancy.
6. The European Parliament shall choose its Speaker and other Officers from among its Members.
7. The European Parliament shall have the sole power of Impeachment.

Art. 76 The European Council

1. The Member States and their Governments shall participate, through the European Council, in the legislative process of the European Union. They shall do so by delegating Representatives to the European Council assemblies.
2. There shall be two types of European Council assemblies, namely:
 - (a) Summits
 - (b) Committee assemblies

Each assembly shall be responsible for legislation in the areas assigned to it.

3. The Member States shall be represented at the Summits by their elected Head of State or Government. The Summits shall be responsible for legislating in the fields of Constitutional Amendments, Restrictions on Basic Rights, Impeachment, the appointment of the Vice President of the European Union, the appointment of the Judges to the General Court of the European Union, and granting temporary additional powers to the Office of Crisis Management.
4. The Member States shall be represented in Committee assemblies by a delegated Representative, delegated to the assembly based on the policy area under discussion. Each of the delegated Representatives represents their Member State and the wishes of its people, Legislature, and Government; and shall have one Vote. They shall be furthermore accountable to their national Legislature. Committee assemblies shall legislate in all areas where Summits are not responsible.
5. The Vice President of the European Union shall be the president of the European Council Summits, but shall have no Vote. The Presidency of the Committee assemblies shall rotate among the Member States every six months.
6. The European Council shall, with a simple majority, choose its officers.
7. There shall be three voting methods in European Council assemblies, the voting method shall be one of the following;
 - (a) A simple majority shall be reached if the majority of the Representatives vote in favour.
 - (b) A qualified majority shall be reached if 55 per cent of the Representatives, who represent at least 65 per cent of the European Union population, vote in favour.
 - (c) A double-qualified majority shall be reached if two-thirds of the Representatives, who represent 75 per cent of the European Union population, vote in favour.

The law shall specify which method shall be used in the case in question. In all cases not specially specified, a qualified majority needs to be reached. Legislation shall be passed if the necessary majority is reached.

8. Summits shall have the sole power to try all Impeachments.
9. To all sessions of the European Council, the Governments of each Member State may delegate an additional Specialist, depending on the subject under discussion, who may take part in the meetings and debates; and advise the Representatives of the European Council. However, no such Specialist shall have the right to vote in the European Council.
10. The European Council shall ensure that national legislatures are given adequate time to express their opinions and positions on bills or topics under discussion.

Art. 77 General Referendums

1. Legislative power shall, in cases specified by this Constitution, be conferred upon the citizens of the European Union directly. The exercise of this power shall be conducted through general referendums.
2. Any citizen entitled to vote for the European Parliament has the right to vote in general referendums.
3. A General Referendum shall be considered carried when it satisfies the participation and majority requirements laid down by this Constitution.
4. The European Congress shall enact laws regulating the procedure of general referendums, including the verification of signatures, the conduct of the vote, public information, campaign rules, and the certification of results.
5. A General Referendum shall be organised and supervised by the European Election Office in cooperation with the competent authorities of the Member States. The voting shall be free, universal, equal, direct, and secret.

Art. 78 Elections of the European Congress

1. The times, places, and manner of holding elections and delegating the Representatives of the European Council shall be prescribed in each Member State by the Legislature thereof.
2. The European Congress shall determine the time of holding Elections for the Members of the European Parliament. It shall make sure that at least two years elapse between the election of the Members of the European Parliament and the election of the President

of the European Union. The places and manner of holding Elections for Members of the European Parliament shall be prescribed in each Member State by the Legislature thereof; however, the European Congress may at any time by Law make or alter such Regulations.

3. The European Congress shall assemble at least once every Year, and such meeting shall be on the last Monday in January unless they shall by Law appoint a different Day.

Art. 79 Rules of the European Congress

1. Each House of the European Congress shall be the judge of the elections, returns, and qualifications of its Members or Representatives, and a majority of each shall constitute a quorum to do business; but a smaller number may adjourn from day to day and may be authorised to compel the attendance of absent Members, in such manner and under such penalties as each House may provide.
2. Each House of the European Congress may determine the Rules of its Proceedings, punish its Members or Representatives for disorderly behaviour, and, in the case of the European Parliament, with the concurrence of two-thirds and a minimum of one Member per Member State, expel a Member.
3. The sittings of each House are public.
4. No person may be a member of both Houses at the same time.
5. The decisions of each House are not valid if the majority of the Members or Representatives are not present.
6. Each House of the European Congress shall keep a journal of its proceedings and, from time to time, publish the same, except in such parts as may in their judgment require secrecy, and the Yeas and Nays of the Members of either House on any question shall, at the desire of one-fifth of those present, be entered on the journal.
7. Neither House, during the Session of Congress, shall, without the consent of the other, adjourn for more than three days, nor to any other place than that in which the two Houses shall be sitting.

Art. 80 Compensation and Privileges of the Members of the European Congress

1. The Representatives of the European Council and the Members of the European Parliament shall receive compensation for their services, to be ascertained by law and paid out of the Treasury of the European Union. They shall, in all cases, except for Treason,

Felony, and Breach of the Peace, be privileged from Arrest during their attendance at the sessions of their respective Houses, and in going to and returning from the same; and for any speech or debate in either House, they shall not be questioned in any other place.

2. No Representative of the European Council or Member of the European Parliament shall, during the time for which he was delegated or elected, be appointed to any civil Office under the authority of the European Union, which shall have been created, or the emoluments thereto shall have been increased during such time, and no Person holding any Office under the European Union shall be a Representative or Member of either House during his continuance in Office.

Art. 81 Legislative process

1. Legislation may be introduced by the President of the European Union, by a Member of the European Congress, by a Member of the legislature of any Member State, or by the people directly by proposing a Bill drawn up in sections and signed by at least three hundred thousand voters.
2. A Bill introduced in the European Congress shall, in both Houses, under their rules of procedure, be scrutinised by a Committee and then by the whole House, which shall consider it section by section, after which both Houses may propose Amendments to the Bill. When the Bill is finalised, it must be put to a final vote in both Houses.
3. A Bill shall only pass the final vote if the majority of the European Parliament and a qualified majority of the European Council support it.
4. Every Bill which shall have passed the European Parliament and the European Council, shall, before it becomes a Law, be presented to the President of the European Union: If he approves the Bill he shall sign it, but if not he shall return it, with his Objections to the European Parliament, who shall enter the Objections at large on their Journal, and proceed to reconsider it. If, after such Reconsideration, two-thirds of the Members shall agree to pass the Bill, it shall be sent, together with the Objections, to the European Council, by which it shall likewise be reconsidered, and if approved by a double-qualified majority of the Members, it shall become a Law. But in all such Cases, the Votes of both Houses shall be determined by Yeas and Nays, and the Names of the Persons voting for and against the Bill shall be entered in the Journal of each House respectively. If any Bill shall not be returned by the President within ten weekdays after it shall have been presented to him, the Same shall be a Law, in like Manner as if he had signed it, unless the European Congress by their Adjournment prevent its Return, in which Case it shall not be a Law.
5. A general referendum must be held to pass a law ratifying an international treaty, accession to organisations for collective security, or accession to supranational communities.

The referendum shall be considered to have been carried if the majority of those eligible have voted and a majority of valid votes have been achieved.

6. A general referendum may be held to pass a Bill put forward to the European Congress when so requested by one million voters or the Legislature of one third of the Member States. The referendum shall be considered to have been carried if the majority of those eligible have voted and a majority of valid votes have been achieved.
7. A general referendum may be held to repeal, in whole or in part, a law or a measure having the force of law, when so requested by five hundred thousand voters or the Legislature of one third of the Member States. The referendum shall be considered to have been carried if two-thirds of those eligible have voted and a majority of valid votes have been achieved.
8. No referendum may be held on a law regulating taxes, the budget, amnesty, or pardon. No referendum shall be held that violates the Limits of the Legislative powers of the European Union.
9. The legislatures of the Member States shall be fully informed of the debates, negotiations, and amendments of all Bill's.
10. No Order, Resolution, or Vote, except on a question of Adjournment shall become Law without going through the whole Legislative process.

Art. 82 Exclusive Legislative Power of the European Congress

1. The European Congress shall have exclusive legislative power concerning:
 - (a) foreign affairs and defence, including protection of the civilian population uniformly throughout the European Union;
 - (b) European Union citizenship;
 - (c) freedom of movement, passports, residency registration and identity cards, immigration, emigration and extradition;
 - (d) currency, money and coinage, weights and measures, and the determination of standards of time;
 - (e) borrowing of money on the credit of the European Union;
 - (f) the unity of the customs and trading area, treaties regarding commerce and navigation, the free movement of goods, and the exchange of goods and payments with foreign countries, including customs and border protection;
 - (g) promotion and the progress of science and useful arts, by securing for limited times to authors and inventors the exclusive right to their respective writings and discoveries;

- (h) safeguarding European cultural assets against removal from the union;
- (i) air transport;
- (j) the legal relations of persons employed by the European Union and by European Union corporations under public law;
- (k) statistics for European Union purposes;
- (l) the law on weapons and explosives;
- (m) declaration of war, granting of letters of marque and reprisal, and making of rules concerning captures on land and water;
- (n) providing and maintaining the armed forces;
- (o) making of rules for the government and regulation of the armed forces;

However, it shall in all cases consult the Member States in due time, hear their opinions, and make sure that their interests are taken into account.

2. The European Congress shall have the power to collect the contributions of the Member States and to lay duties, to pay the debts, and provide for the common defence and general welfare of the European Union; but such contributions and duties shall be uniform throughout the European Union.
3. The European Congress may also make legislation in all other instances after compromising with Member States, while respecting the limits of its legislative power. These shall become the joint legislative powers.
4. When legislating on the specified cases outlined in Article 81, Paragraph (1); (a), (b), (c), (d), (e), (m), (n), (o), a double-qualified majority shall be necessary for a Bill to pass the European Council.

Art. 83 Limits on Legislative Power

1. The privilege of the Basic Rights of Justice shall not be suspended, unless, in cases of rebellion or invasion, the public safety may require it.
2. No bill of attainder or ex post facto law shall be passed.
3. No capitation, or other direct tax shall be laid, unless in proportion to the census or enumeration herein before directed to be taken.
4. No tax or duty shall be laid on articles exported from any Member State.
5. No preference shall be given by any regulation of commerce or revenue to the trading posts of one Member State over those of another; nor shall goods bound to, or from, one Member State be obliged to enter, clear, or pay duties in another.

6. No money shall be drawn from the Treasury of the European Union, but in consequence of appropriations made by law; a regular statement and account of the receipts and expenditures of all public money shall be published from time to time.
7. No title of nobility shall be granted by the European Union: And no person holding any office of profit or trust under them, shall, without the consent of the European Congress, accept any present, emolument, office, or title, of any kind whatever, from any foreign state.
8. The European Congress and the legislatures of the Member States shall exercise legislation jointly in all instances except the Exclusive legislative areas of the European Congress, respecting the Limits on Legislative Power.

Art. 84 Impeachment

1. The President of the European Union, Vice President, and all Civil Officers of the European Union shall be removed from Office on Impeachment for, and Conviction of, Treason, Bribery, or other high Crimes and Misdemeanours.
2. The European Parliament may impeach any Civil Officer of the European Union before the European Council for wilful violation of the Constitution of the European Union or of any other European Union law. The motion of impeachment must be supported by at least one-third of the Members of the European Parliament. The decision to impeach shall require a majority of fifty-five per cent of the Members of the European Parliament. The case for impeachment shall be presented before the European Council by a person commissioned by the impeaching body.
3. The European Council shall, when sitting to try an Impeachment, be on Oath or Affirmation. When the President of the European Union is tried, the President of the European Court of Justice shall preside: And no Person shall be convicted without the Concurrence of a qualified majority of the Representatives present.
4. If the European Council finds the Civil Officer in question guilty of a willful violation of the Constitution of the European Union or any other European Union law, it may declare that he has forfeited his office. After the President of the European Union has been impeached, the European Council may issue an interim order preventing him from exercising his functions. Judgment in Cases of Impeachment shall not extend further than to removal from Office, and disqualification to hold and enjoy any Office of Honour, Trust, or Profit under the European Union: but the Party convicted shall nevertheless be liable and subject to Indictment, Trial, Judgment and Punishment, according to Law.

Executive powers

Art. 85 The Executive powers of the European Union

1. All executive powers herein granted shall be vested in the President of the European Union, the European Commission, and the Governments of the Member States.

The President of the European Union

Art. 86 Election, Term, and Incompatibilities of the President of the European Union

1. The President of the European Union shall be elected every fifth year by the people of the European Union via universal suffrage in a personal, free, equal, and secret vote.
2. No Person shall become the President of the European Union who shall not have attained the age of thirty Years and been fifteen years a citizen of the European Union.
3. No person holding an office of trust or profit under the European Union or its Member States shall become President of the European Union.
4. The European Congress shall determine the time of the election of the President of the European Union; the Day shall be the same throughout the European Union. The election of the new President shall be held no fewer than thirty days and no more than fifty days before the expiry of the term of the President in office.
5. To become a candidate for the Presidential election, a person must gather two hundred thousand recommendations, of which at least seven times twenty thousand must be from seven different Member States; at least twenty thousand from each. After this, the President of the European Union shall be elected from the candidates by an absolute majority of votes cast. If, before the first round of voting, any of the candidates dies or becomes incapacitated, the European Congress shall declare the election to be postponed. A second ballot is necessary if a majority of votes cast is not obtained on the first ballot; the second ballot shall take place on the fourteenth day thereafter. Only the two candidates polling the greatest number of votes in the first ballot, after any withdrawal of better-placed candidates, may stand in the second ballot. In the event of the death or incapacitation of either of the two candidates in the lead after the first round of voting before any withdrawals, the European Congress shall declare that the electoral process must be repeated in full; the same shall apply in the event of the death or incapacitation of either of the two candidates still standing on the second round of voting.

6. No person shall be elected to the office of the President more than twice, and no person who has held the office of President, or acted as President, for more than two years of a term to which some other person was elected President shall be elected to the office of the President more than once.
7. No person shall be elected to a second term as President, if not directly reelected, after his/her first term.

Art. 87 Removal of the President of the European Union from office

1. In case of the removal of the President of the European Union from office, or of his death, resignation, or inability to discharge the powers and duties of the said office, the same shall devolve on the Vice President of the European Union, and the European Congress may by Law provide for the case of removal, death, resignation or inability, both of the President of the European Union and Vice President of the European Union, declaring what Officer shall then act as President of the European Union, and such Officer shall act accordingly, until the disability be removed, or a President shall be elected.

Art. 88 Oath of office of the President of the European Union

1. The President of the European Union shall ensure due respect for the Constitution of the European Union. He shall ensure, by arbitration, the proper functioning of the public authorities and the continuity of the European Union. He shall be the guarantor of the sovereignty of the Member States, their territorial integrity, and due respect for the Treaties.
2. On assuming his office, the President of the European Union shall take the following oath: "I do solemnly swear (or affirm) that I will dedicate my efforts to the well-being of the European people, promote their welfare, protect them from harm, uphold and defend the Constitution of the European Union and the laws of the Union, perform my duties conscientiously and do justice to all."

Art. 89 Presidential Power

1. The President of the European Union shall be the Head of State of the European Union.
2. The President of the European Union shall appoint the Commissioners. He may also terminate the appointment of Commissioners if he considers that their duties have not been fulfilled properly, in which case he must appoint someone else to fill the Office of the European Commission vacated.

3. The President of the European Union shall lead the European Commission and decide on its political direction.
4. The President of the European Union shall lead the Bureau of the Presidency, whose purpose shall be to assist the President in the performance of his duties.
5. The President of the European Union shall;
 - (a) promulgate laws and issue decrees having the force of law and regulations.
 - (b) call a general referendum in the cases provided for by the Constitution of the European Union.
 - (c) appoint European Union officials in the cases provided for by the law.
6. The President of the European Union may;
 - (a) send messages to the European Congress.
 - (b) as written in (Article 80 Legislative process), return a Bill to the European Congress.
 - (c) propose a Bill.
7. The President of the European Union shall represent the Federation in international law, receive diplomatic representatives, and appoint the Ambassadors of the European Union. He shall conclude treaties with foreign states on behalf of the European Union and shall ratify international treaties which have, where required, been authorised by the European Congress.
8. The President of the European Union shall be Commander in Chief of the European Union Armed Forces in wartime. He shall make declarations of war as has been agreed on by the European Congress.
9. The President of the European Union shall have the Power to grant reprieves and pardons for offences against the European Union, except in cases of Impeachment, and such reprieves and pardons shall be made public.

Art. 90 The Vice President of the European Union

1. No Person shall become the Vice President of the European Union who shall not have attained the age of thirty Years and been fifteen years a citizen of the European Union.
2. No person holding an office of trust or profit under the European Union or its Member States shall become Vice President of the European Union.
3. The Vice President of the European Union cannot come from the same Member State as the President of the European Union.

4. No person shall be elected to the office of the Vice President more than twice, and no person who has held the office of President for more than two years of a term may become Vice President of the European Union.
5. On assuming his office, the President of the European Union shall recommend a person who fulfils the requirements as Vice President of the European Union. The European Council shall then have a vote as to whether the candidate is satisfactory or not. The candidate will have passed the vote if a qualified majority of the Representatives of the European Council vote in his favour. If the candidate does not pass the vote, the President shall recommend another person who fulfils the requirements. The European Council shall then have a vote as to whether the candidate is satisfactory or not. If, after the second vote, there still isn't a Vice President, each Representative of the European Council shall vote for one of the two candidates. The candidate with the most votes shall become the Vice President of the European Union. In the case of a draw, the Representatives representing a larger share of the European Union population shall win the vote. So the candidate they represented shall become the Vice President of the European Union. Neither the President of the European Union nor the European Council may adjourn for more than one week.

Art. 91 Compensation and Privileges of the President and the Vice President of the European Union

1. The President of the European Union and the Vice President of the European Union shall, at stated times, receive for their services, a compensation, which shall neither be increased nor diminished during the period for which they shall have been elected, and they shall not receive within that period any other emolument from the European Union, or any of its Member States.

The European Commission

Art. 92 Members of the European Commission

1. The heads of the Offices of the European Union shall be called the Commissioners.
2. The Commissioners shall be responsible for their respective Offices of the European Union.
3. The European Commission shall consist of the Commissioners of the Offices of the European Union. There shall be 25 Basic Offices. These shall be;
 - (a) The Office of Finance
 - (b) The Office of Foreign Affairs

- (c) The Office of Defence
 - (d) The Office of Justice
 - (e) The Office of Interior
 - (f) The Office of Economics
 - (g) The Office of Agriculture
 - (h) The Office of Labour
 - (i) The Office of Health
 - (j) The Office of Infrastructure
 - (k) The Office of Transportation
 - (l) The Office of Energy
 - (m) The Office of Innovation, Research and Development
 - (n) The Office of Education
 - (o) The Office of Family Affairs
 - (p) The Office of Seniors
 - (q) The Office of Environment
 - (r) The Office of Digitisation
 - (s) The Office of Housing and Urban Development
 - (t) The Office of Culture
 - (u) The Office of Science
 - (v) The Office of Crisis Management
 - (w) The Office of Intelligence
 - (x) The Office of Values and Transparency
 - (y) The Office of Democracy and Demography
4. The President may create Special Offices which shall exist during his mandate with the consent of the European Parliament. The Special Offices shall have the power that the European Parliament concedes to them.

Art. 93 Appointment, Term, Removal, and Compensation of the Members of the European Commission

1. The President of the European Union shall appoint the Commissioner of each of the Basic Offices, where required, with the consent of the European Parliament. When appointing a Commissioner, he shall consider expertise and experience.

2. No more than two Commissioners of the Basic Offices may come from the same Member State, and no Commissioner of the Basic Offices may come from the same Member State as the President of the European Union or the Vice President of the European Union.
3. The President of the European Union shall appoint the Commissioner of each of the Special Offices.
4. Commissioners serve their respective Offices of the European Commission until they are removed or until the mandate of the President of the European Union who appointed them lasts. No person may be Commissioner of the European Commission for more than ten years.
5. If the President of the European Union is dissatisfied with the performance of an Office of the European Commission, then the responsible Commissioner shall be removed and the President of the European Union shall appoint a new Commissioner to the Office of the European Commission in question.
6. No person holding an office of trust or profit under the European Union or its Member States shall become a Commissioner of the European Commission.
7. No person shall become a Commissioner of the European Union who shall not have been six years a European Union citizen.
8. The Commissioners of the European Union shall, at stated times, receive for their services a compensation, which shall neither be increased nor diminished during the period for which they shall have been appointed, and they shall not receive within that period any other emolument from the European Union or any of its Member States.

Art. 94 Oath of office of the Members of the European Commission

1. The Commissioners shall ensure the proper function of the authorities entrusted to them.
2. On assuming their office, the Commissioners of the European Union shall take the following oath: “I do solemnly swear (or affirm) that I will execute my Office conscientiously, dedicate my efforts to the well-being of the European People, promote their welfare, protect them from harm, uphold and defend the Constitution of the European Union and the laws of the Union, that I will execute my duties to the best of my ability and in so far as the power of my Office allows it.”

Art. 95 Power of the Commissioners

1. The Commissioners have the freedom to carry out the duties of their Office independently within the boundaries set by the President of the European Union.

2. The Commissioners of the European Union shall aim to resolve disputes between the European Union and the Governments of the Member States.
3. Commissioners are the head of their respective Offices.
4. Any Commissioner of the European Union may propose a Bill.

The Governments of the Member States

Art. 96 The Governments of the Member States and Municipalities

1. The Governments of the Member States are responsible for the implementation and execution of the European Union laws in their jurisdiction unless this Constitution or European Union laws require otherwise.
2. Governments have the freedom to set up their authorities and the administrative processes to execute European Union laws unless this Constitution or European Union laws require otherwise.
3. Governments that fail to implement and execute the European Union laws in due time may be sanctioned by the European Commission.
4. The Governments of the Member States shall guarantee Municipalities the right to regulate all local affairs within their responsibility within the limits prescribed by the laws.

Judicial powers

Art. 97 The Judicial powers of the European Union

1. All judicial power given shall be based on law, it shall be vested in the Judges, and it shall be exercised by the European Court of Justice, the General Court of the European Union, and by the courts of the Member States.
2. The organisation and procedure of the courts shall be governed by law.

The European Court of Justice

Art. 98 Jurisdiction of the European Court of Justice

1. The European Court of Justice shall be the highest Court of the European Union and its Member States. Its sentence shall be final and not modifiable.
2. The European Court of Justice hears disputes concerning violations of:
 - (a) The Constitution of the European Union;
 - (b) European Union law;
 - i. interpreting the European Union law,
 - ii. enforcing the law,
 - iii. annulling European Union legal acts,
 - iv. ensuring the European Union and its Member States take action,
 - v. sanctioning European Union and Member State institutions.
 - (c) international law;
 - (d) inter-Member State law;
 - (e) European Union trans Member State laws;
 - (f) Member State constitutional rights;
 - (g) the autonomy of the communes and other Member State guarantees in favour of public law corporations;
 - (h) European Union and Member State provisions on political rights.
3. The organisation and procedure of the European Court of Justice shall be governed by European Union law.

Art. 99 Appointment and term of Judges of the European Court of Justice

1. Each Member State of the European Union may appoint one Judge to the European Court of Justice.
2. The appointment process of the Judges of the European Court of Justice shall be as follows:
 - (a) The Government of the Member State whose judicial position shall have been vacated shall nominate a Judge to the position who meets the conditions to become a Judge of the European Court of Justice. The Legislature of the Member State shall then hold a vote to confirm the nominee.
 - (b) The Member State shall then recommend this person to the European Parliament. The Parliament shall then hold a vote to confirm the nominee. The nominee is confirmed if he or she gets a majority of the votes.
 - (c) If the nominee is turned down by the European Parliament (does not get a majority of the votes), the Government of the Member State shall have to nominate someone else, in which case the nomination process starts again from the beginning.
 - (d) The law shall provide for cases where a Member State fails to fill a vacancy for more than two years, taking into account the adjournment of the European Parliament.
3. The term of a Judge of the European Court of Justice shall be twenty years.
4. No person shall become the Judge of the European Court of Justice who shall not have attained the age of fifty years and been twenty years a European Union citizen.
5. No person shall become the Judge of the European Court of Justice who shall not have been a Judge of the General Court of the European Union for twelve years.
6. No person holding an office of trust or profit under the European Union or its Member States shall become a Judge of the European Court of Justice.

Art. 100 Members of the European Court of Justice

1. The Judges of the European Court of Justice shall be divided into three groups, each group shall serve one of the Chambers of the European Court of Justice, these shall be;
 - (a) The I. Chamber of the Constitutional Court of the European Union
 - (b) The II. Chamber of the Constitutional Court of the European Union
 - (c) The Court of Final Appeal

2. The membership of a Chamber will rotate among the Member States according to the following process: An Order shall be established among the Member States, following which the Judges of the first nine Member States in this Order shall become the Judges of the I. Chamber of the Constitutional Court of the European Union; the Judges of the next nine Member States shall become the Judges of the II. Chamber of the Constitutional Court of the European Union; and the Judges of the remaining Member States shall become the Judges of the Court of Final Appeal.

Every two years, the first two Judges in the Order in each Chamber shall rotate according to the following procedure. The Judges who had previously been the Judges of the I. Chamber of the Constitutional Court of the European Union shall become the Judges of the II. Chamber of the Constitutional Court of the European Union, the Judges who had previously been the Judges of the II. Chamber of the Constitutional Court of the European Union shall become the Judges of the Court of Final Appeal, and the Judges who had previously been the Judges of the Court of Final Appeal shall become the Judges of the I. Chamber of the Constitutional Court of the European Union.

3. The European Court of Justice shall name its president, who shall serve for a term of five years.

Art. 101 Structure of the European Court of Justice

1. The European Court of Justice shall have its own administration.
2. The European Court of Justice shall be made up of the following three Chambers:
 - (a) The I. Chamber of the Constitutional Court of the European Union
 - (b) The II. Chamber of the Constitutional Court of the European Union
 - (c) The Court of Final Appeal

Each Chamber shall judge in the specific questions assigned it by this Constitution or any other Law.

3. The I. and the II. Chambers of the Constitutional Court of the European Union shall take turns ruling on the arising questions surrounding:
 - (a) the interpretation of this Constitution of the European Union in the event of disputes concerning the extent of the rights and duties of European Union institutions or other parties vested with rights of their own by this Constitution of the European Union or on the rules of procedure of the European Union institutions;
 - (b) the formal or substantive compatibility of European Union law or Member State law with this Constitution of the European Union or the compatibility of Member State law with other European Union law;

- (c) the compatibility of new European Union laws with the Constitution of the European Union;
 - (d) the rights and duties of the European Union and the Member States, especially in the execution of European Union law by the Member States and in the exercise of European Union oversight;
 - (e) public law between the European Union and the Member States, between different Member States or within a Member State, unless there is recourse to another court;
 - (f) constitutional complaints filed by municipalities or associations of municipalities on the ground that their right to self-government has been infringed by a law (in the case of infringement by a Member State law, a complaint can only be filed if the law cannot be challenged in the constitutional court of the Member State);
 - (g) violations of someone's Basic rights;
 - (h) violations of the Constitution of the European Union;
 - (i) the amendments of the Constitution of the European Union;
 - (j) violations of Member State Constitutions, amendments of Member State Constitutions, and whether the Member State Constitutions meet the requirements of the Constitution of the European Union;
 - (k) constitutional complaints filed by associations concerning their non-recognition as political parties for an election to the European Parliament;
 - (l) other instances provided for in this Constitution of the European Union.
4. The Court of Final Appeal shall hear appeals against the decisions of the General Court of the European Union. Its primary function shall be to act as the ultimate authority on appeals in various types of cases. It shall be responsible for ensuring the consistent and fair application of the law, correcting errors made by lower courts, and providing legal clarity to the public. The Court of Final Appeal shall focus on issues of law and legal precedent, ensuring a uniform interpretation of the law throughout the European Union; it shall not rule on Constitutional questions.

The General Court of the European Union

Art. 102 Jurisdiction of the General Court of the European Union

1. The General Court of the European Union hears disputes concerning violations of:
 - (a) The Constitution of the European Union;
 - (b) European Union law;

- (c) interpreting the European Union law;
- (d) inter-Member State law;
- (e) European Union trans Member State laws;
- (f) international law;
- (g) the autonomy of the communes and other Member State guarantees in favour of public law corporations.
- (h) and in other cases specified in the European Union law.

Art. 103 Appointment and term of the Judges of the General Court of the European Union

1. The General Court of the European Union shall be made up of ninety Judges; however, the European Congress may extend this number if it finds it necessary.
2. One-third of the Judges shall be appointed by the President of the European Union, one-third by the European Council, and one-third by the Supreme Courts of the Member States. The President of the European Union, the European Council, and the Supreme Courts of the Member States must all appoint at least one Judge from each of the Member States. All appointments shall then need to be confirmed by the European Parliament.
3. The term of a Judge of the General Court of the European Union shall be twelve years, and no one may be appointed more than twice to the position of Judge of the General Court of the European Union.
4. The Judges of the General Court of the European Union shall be chosen from among Judges, including those retired, of the ordinary and administrative higher Courts, university professors of law, and lawyers with at least twenty years of practice.
5. No person shall become the Judge of the General Court of the European Union who shall not have attained the age of forty years and been ten years a European Union citizen.
6. No person holding an office of trust or profit under the European Union or its Member States shall become a Judge of the General Court of the European Union.

Art. 104 Judges of the General Court of the European Union

1. The Judges of the General Court of the European Union shall be divided into panels of five Judges. Each panel shall hear cases from a specified part of the jurisdiction.
2. The General Court of the European Union shall name its president, who shall serve for a term of four years.

Art. 105 Structure of the General Court of the European Union

1. The General Court of the European Union shall organise itself into panels and shall assign each panel a special part of the jurisdiction of the General Court of the European Union.
2. The General Court of the European Union shall have its own administration.

The courts of the Member States**Art. 106 Jurisdiction of the courts of the Member States**

1. All Member States of the European Union shall appoint judicial authorities to judge civil and public law disputes and criminal law cases. If the judicial authority is unsure of a sentence, it may ask for the review of a higher court or if one of the parties to the case is uncertain of the sentence of the court, it may sue the court at a higher court.
2. The Member State judicial authorities are bound by Member State and European Union law.

Art. 107 Structure of the courts of the Member States

1. All Member States shall have a supreme Court this Supreme Court shall be the highest Court in the Member State in question it shall be inferior only to the European Court of Justice, the General Court of the European Union, and the Regional Court (s) of which the Member State in question is a member (if such a court exists).
2. The organisation and procedure of Member State courts shall be governed by Member State and European Union law.
3. Member States of the European Union may join together to create Regional Courts whose verdict is higher than that of the Courts of the Member States but lower than that of the General Court of the European Union.
4. The Member State and Regional Courts shall have their own administration.

Judiciary**Art. 108 Judicial independence**

1. All Judges of the European Union and its Member States shall be independent and subject only to the law.

2. All Judges of the European Union and its Member States appointed permanently to positions as their primary occupation may be involuntarily dismissed, permanently or temporarily suspended, transferred, or retired before the expiry of their term of office only by virtue of judicial decision and only for the reasons and in the manner specified by the laws. In the event of changes in the structure of courts or their districts, judges may be transferred to another court or removed from office, provided they retain their full salary.

Art. 109 Impeachment of Judges

1. The Judges of the European Union shall be removed from Office on Impeachment for, and Conviction of, Treason, Bribery, or other high Crimes and Misdemeanours.
2. The Judges of the Member States and the Judges of the Regional Courts may be removed from Office on Impeachment for, and Conviction of, Treason, Bribery, or other high Crimes and Misdemeanours.

Art. 110 Safeguarding the Basic Rights of Justice

1. All Judges of the European Union shall be subject only to the Law and the Constitution of the European Union.
2. All Judges of the European Union shall conduct and conclude debates according to the Basic Rights of Justice.

Art. 111 Ban on extraordinary courts

1. Extraordinary courts shall not be allowed. No one may be removed from the jurisdiction of his lawful judge.
2. Courts for particular fields of law may be established only by a law.

Art. 112 Compensation and Privileges of Judges

1. All Judges of the European Union and its Member States shall, at stated times, receive for their services a compensation, which shall neither be increased nor diminished during the period for which they shall have been appointed, and they shall not receive within that period any other emolument from the European Union or any of its Member States.
2. All Judges of the European Union shall, in all cases, except Treason, Felony, and Breach of the Peace, be privileged from Arrest during their attendance at the debate of their respective Courts, and in going to and returning from the same.

Member States

Art. 113 Cooperation between the European Union and the Member States

1. The European Union and the Member States shall support each other in the fulfilment of their duties and shall generally cooperate.
2. The European Union and the Member States owe each other a duty of consideration and support. They shall provide each other with administrative assistance and mutual judicial assistance.
3. Disputes between Member States or between Member States and the European Union shall, wherever possible, be resolved by negotiation or mediation.
4. In the cases specified by the Constitution of the European Union, the Member States shall participate in the European Union decision-making process, and in particular in the legislative process.
5. The European Union shall inform the Member States of its intentions fully and in good time. It shall consult the Member States where their interests are affected.
6. The Member States shall implement European Union law in accordance with the Constitution of the European Union and European Union law.
7. The European Union and the Member States may together agree that the Member States should achieve specific goals in the implementation of European Union law and may to this end conduct programs that receive financial support from the European Union.
8. The European Union shall allow the Member States all possible discretion to organise their own affairs and shall take account of Member State particularities.

Art. 114 Inter Member State agreements

1. The Member States of the European Union may enter into agreements with each other and establish common organisations and institutions. In particular, they may jointly undertake tasks of regional importance together.
2. The European Union may participate in such organisations or institutions within the scope of its powers.
3. Agreements between the Member States of the European Union must not be contrary to the law, to the interests of the European Union, or the rights of other Member States. The European Union must be notified of such agreements.

4. The Member States may by inter Member State agreement authorise inter Member State bodies to issue legislative provisions that implement an inter Member State agreement, provided the agreement:
 - (a) has been approved under the same procedure that applies to other legislation;
 - (b) determines the basic content of the provisions.
5. The Member States shall comply with inter Member State law.
6. At the request of interested Member States, the European Union may declare inter Member State agreements to be generally binding or require Member States to participate in inter Member State agreements.
7. A declaration of general application is made in the form of a European Union decree.
8. The law shall specify the requirements for a declaration of general application and a participation requirement and regulate the procedure.

Art. 115 Autonomy of Member States

1. The European Union shall respect the autonomy and sovereignty of the Member States.
2. The European Union shall leave the Member States sufficient tasks of their own and respect their organisational autonomy. It shall leave the Member States with sufficient sources of finance and contribute towards ensuring that they have the financial resources required to fulfil their tasks.
3. The Member States decide on the duties that they must fulfil within the scope of their powers.

Art. 116 Privileges and Immunity's, Extradition

1. The Citizens of each Member State shall be entitled to all Privileges and Immunities of Citizens in the several Member States.
2. A Person charged in any Member State with Treason, Felony, or other Crime, who shall flee from Justice, and be found in another Member State, shall on demand of the executive authority of the Member State from which he fled, be delivered up, to be removed to the Member State having Jurisdiction of the Crime.

Art. 117 Limits on Member States

1. European Union law takes precedence over any conflicting provision of Member State law.
2. The European Union shall ensure that the Member States comply with European Union law.
3. No Member State of the European Union shall, without the consent of the European Congress, maintain an army; keep troops, or ships of war, keep large weapons in times of peace, enter into any agreement or compact with another Member State, or with a foreign Power, or engage in war, unless invaded, or in such imminent danger as will not admit of delay.
4. No Member State of the European Union shall, without the consent of the European Congress, lay any duty of tonnage, lay any imposts or duties on imports or exports, except what may be absolutely necessary for executing its inspection laws: and the net produce of all duties and imposts, laid by any Member State on imports or exports, shall be for the use of the Treasury of the European Union; and all such laws shall be subject to the revision and control of the European Congress.
5. No Member State of the European Union shall enter into any Treaty, Alliance, or Confederation; grant letters of marque and reprisal; coin money; emit bills of credit; pass any Bill of attainder, ex post facto Law, or Law impairing the Obligation of Contracts, or grant any Title of Nobility not already given before this Constitution of the European Union was signed.

Art. 118 Guarantees to the Member States

1. The European Union shall fulfil the duties that are assigned to it by the Constitution of the European Union.
2. The European Union shall guarantee to every Member State in this European Union a democratic republican form of government based on the Rule of Law, and shall protect each of them against invasion; and on the application of the Legislature, or of the Executive (when the Legislature cannot be convened) against domestic violence.
3. The European Union only undertakes tasks that the Member States are unable to perform or which require uniform regulation by the European Union.
4. The collective body that benefits from a public service bears the costs thereof.
5. The collective body that bears the costs of a public service may decide on the nature of that service.

6. Universally provided services shall be made available to every person in a comparable manner.
7. State tasks shall be fulfilled economically and in accordance with demand.

Art. 119 Member State constitutions and constitutional order

1. Each Member State shall adopt a democratic constitution that respects the basic rights of the European Union. This requires the approval of the people and must be capable of being revised if the majority of those eligible to vote so request.
2. Each Member State constitution shall require the guarantee of the European Union. The European Union shall guarantee a constitution provided it is not contrary to European Union law.
3. The European Union shall defend the Member States' constitutional order.
4. The European Union shall intervene when public order in a Member State is disrupted or under threat and the Member State in question is not able to maintain order alone or with the aid of other Member States.

Art. 120 Admission of new Member States or Exit of a Member State

1. New Member States may be admitted by the European Congress into this European Union, but no new Member State shall be formed or erected within the Jurisdiction of any other Member State; nor any Member State be formed by the junction of two or more Member States, or Parts of Member States, without the consent of the Legislatures of the Member States concerned as well as of the European Congress.
2. The European Congress decides whether a new Member State is socially, economically, and democratically developed enough to join the European Union.
3. The Legislature of five or more Member States can veto the accession of a new Member State.
4. A new Member State may only join the European Union if it is governed democratically and according to the rule of law and if its basic law or constitution complies with the Constitution of the European Union.
5. A new Member State before it becomes a Member State of the European Union must also hold a national referendum on whether it wishes to join the European Union.

6. A Member State may leave the European Union if a Majority of its residents vote to exit the Union in a referendum. On leaving the European Union the Member State shall lose all the benefits guaranteed by the European Union. It shall withdraw from the common currency the Euro, it shall cease to be part of the Single Market and the customs Union. The European Armed Forces, Frontex and all other European Union Institutions, Offices and Agencies shall cease to operate and withdraw from its territory. From this moment on the Member State need not make further commitments to the European Union budget. The European Congress shall legislate on all additional details, in doing so it shall create a fair and orderly exit procedure for the Member States.

Media powers

Art. 121 Freedom and Privacy of Journalists

1. Everyone shall be free to conduct journalism in the European Union.
2. There shall be no censorship, intimidation, or government interference and the privacy of Journalists shall be respected.
3. Journalists shall be free to investigate and report on matters of public interest, they may criticise people of power and form opinions based on facts.
4. Journalists shall adhere to ethical standards and respect the privacy and dignity of people.
5. Journalists shall make sure they do not misinform their consumers.
6. Information factually proven false may be labelled as fake news. The European Union and its Member States may make news labelled as fake news harder to access and force the source to pay a penalty and write a correction.
7. All media companies, news sources, and state media must make the sources of their statements accessible.
8. The European Union recognises investigative journalism as an essential part of the combat against fraud.

Privately owned Media

Art. 122 Media Diversity

1. The European Union and its Member States shall ensure that there is a wide range of independent news sources, that no media company grows to dominate the media market, and that the media market has a wide range of media companies conducting journalism independently from one another.
2. The European Union shall make sure that none of these characteristics:
 - (a) profit maximising;
 - (b) high barriers to the entry of the media market;
 - (c) news sources owned only by large media companies;
 - (d) only a few media companies doing interviews;
 - (e) only specified media companies getting government ads;

- (f) owners of large media companies supporting specific politicians and political parties;
 - (g) single, few and small quality of news sources;
- resemble the European Union's media market.
3. Media providers will have to ensure transparency of ownership by publicly disclosing such information and take measures to guarantee the independence of individual editorial decisions
 4. The European Union and its Member States shall make sure that governments, politicians, and political parties do not influence the independence of media companies and news sources.

State owned Media

Art. 123 The Media powers of the European Union

1. All Media powers of the European Union shall be vested in the private broadcasters and the Board of the independent state Media. It shall be the duty of the Media to inform the people.
2. The people may always trust the independent reporting of the state Media.

Art. 124 Independence of State Media

1. The European Union and its Member States shall create state-run broadcasting and media.
2. The mission of the state media is to act in the public interest, serving all audiences through the provision of impartial, high-quality, and distinctive output and services that inform, educate, and entertain.
3. State media shall be totally independent, free, easily accessible, and public.

Art. 125 The Public Purposes of State Media

1. The Public Purposes of the State Media are as follows:
 - (a) To provide impartial news and information to help people understand and engage with the world around them: the state Media should provide duly accurate and impartial news, current affairs, and factual programming to build people's understanding of all parts of the Member States, the European Union and the wider world.

Its content should be provided to the highest editorial standards. It should offer a range and depth of analysis and content not widely available from other Member State and European Union news providers, using the highest calibre presenters and journalists, and championing freedom of expression, so that all audiences can engage fully with major local, regional, national, European Union and global issues and participate in the democratic process, at all levels, as active and informed citizens.

- (b) To support learning for people of all ages: the state Media should help everyone learn about different subjects in ways they will find accessible, engaging, inspiring, and challenging. The state Media should provide specialist educational content to help support learning for children and teenagers across the European Union. It should encourage people to explore new subjects and participate in new activities through partnerships with educational, sporting, and cultural institutions.
- (c) To show the most creative, highest quality, and distinctive output and services: the state Media should provide high-quality output in many different genres and across a range of services and platforms which sets the standard in the Member States, the European Union, and internationally. Its services should be distinctive from those provided elsewhere and should take creative risks, even if not all succeed, to develop fresh approaches and innovative content.
- (d) To reflect, represent, and serve the diverse communities of all of the European Union's nations and regions and, in doing so, support the creative economy across the European Union: the state Media should reflect the diversity of the European Union both in its output and services. In doing so, the state Media should accurately and authentically represent and portray the lives of the people of the European Union today, and raise awareness of the different cultures and alternative viewpoints that make up its society. It should ensure that it provides output and services that meet the needs of the European Union's nations, regions, and communities. The state Media should bring people together for shared experiences and help contribute to the social cohesion and well-being of the European Union. In commissioning and delivering output the state Media should invest in the creative economies of each of the nations and contribute to their development.
- (e) To reflect the European Union and its Member States, culture, and values to the world: the state Media should provide high-quality news coverage to international audiences, firmly based on European values of accuracy, impartiality, and fairness. Its international services should put the European Union in a world context, aiding understanding of the European Union as a whole, including its Member States, nations, and regions where appropriate. It should ensure that it produces output and services that will be enjoyed by people in the European Union and globally.

Art. 126 The Financing of State Media

1. The state Media shall put forward a budget plan based on its planned activities. Based on this the Legislature and the Board of the state Media shall agree on a budget. The finances of the State Media shall be stable in the long term.
2. The state Media shall be financed through a tax the amount of which shall be determined by the Legislature and the Board of the state Media based on how much money the state media needs to function as required by the Constitution of the European Union and the law, this tax shall be paid by the people and the Privately owned media companies.
3. The state Media must put forward a budget on how it proposes to spend the money assigned to it. The expenditure of the state Media must be accessible to the public.
4. The Board of the state Media may be made to pay a penalty the amount of which shall be determined by law, if the expenditure of the state Media does not agree with toes put forward in its budget.

Art. 127 The Structure and Members of State Media

1. State Media shall be governed by the Board.
2. The Board shall make its decisions according to the majority of the Board members.
3. The Board shall be a group of Journalists, Reporters and Editors appointed for a minimum of six years. Half the Board shall be appointed by the legislature, while the other half, shall be elected by the employees of the state Media. The board shall consist of a minimum of fifteen members.
4. No person may be removed from his post in the Board while his term lasts unless Impeached.
5. The employees of the state Media work until their contract expires or they are fired.

Art. 128 The Duties of State Media

1. Acting in the public interest
 - (a) The state Media must act in the public interest.
 - (b) The state Media must ensure that the benefits (whether direct or indirect) of decisions relating to the fulfilment of its Mission and the promotion of Public Purposes outweigh the costs (whether direct or indirect) and in doing so, have regard to economic, social and cultural benefits and costs.

2. Engagement with the public

- (a) The state Media must carefully and appropriately assess the views and interests of the public and audiences, including licence fee payers, across the whole state.
- (b) The state Media must make arrangements to ensure that the diverse perspectives and interests of the public and audiences, including licence fee payers, across the whole of the state are taken into account in its decision-making.

3. Market impact

- (a) The state Media must have particular regard for the effects of its activities on competition in the European Union and its Member States.

4. Openness, transparency and accountability

- (a) The state Media must observe high standards of openness and seek to maximise transparency and accountability.

5. Partnership

- (a) The state Media must work collaboratively and seek to enter into partnerships with other organisations, particularly in the creative economy, where to do so would be in the public interest.

6. Diversity

- (a) The state Media must ensure it reflects the diverse communities of the whole of the state in the content of its output, the means by which its output and services are delivered (including where its activities are carried out and by whom) and in the organisation and management of the state Media.

7. Technology

- (a) The state Media must promote technological innovation, and maintain a leading role in research and development, that supports the effective fulfilment of its Mission and the promotion of Public Purposes.

8. Stewardship of public money

- (a) The state Media must exercise rigorous stewardship of public money under the following principles.
- (b) Regularity: the management of all of the state Media's resources must accord with the provisions of the Constitution of the European Union and the law.

- (c) Propriety: the management of all of the state Media's resources must meet high standards of public conduct, and robust governance and duly consider the expectations of the Legislature which have been formally communicated to the state Media.
- (d) Value for money: procurement, projects and processes must be systematically evaluated and assessed to provide confidence about suitability, effectiveness, prudence, quality, value and avoidance of error and other waste, taking into account the wider public interest, not just that of the state Media itself.
- (e) Feasibility: proposals using public funds should be implemented accurately, sustainably and to the intended timetable.

Art. 129 Member State state Media

1. All the Member States of the European Union may create state Media corporations.
2. The state Media of the Member States shall be governed according to the Constitution of the European Union, European Union law and the laws of the Member State.

Art. 130 The European Broadcasting Corporation

1. The European Broadcasting Corporation shall be the state Media of the European Union.
2. The European Broadcasting Corporation shall conduct its programs in all the official languages of the European Union.
3. The European Broadcasting Corporation shall function according to the Constitution of the European Union, and European Union law.
4. The Board of the European Broadcasting Corporation shall be made up of twenty-five Journalists. Each Journalist shall be appointed for seven years. Twelve-twelve Journalists shall be appointed by the European Congress and by the employees of the European Broadcasting Corporation. The Board shall then elect a President from outside its Members.
5. The President of the Board shall be elected for a renewable term of three and a half years. He shall be responsible for the transparent functioning of the European Broadcasting Corporation.

Educating powers

Art. 131 The Educating Powers of the European Union

1. Recognising that education and the acquisition of skills, knowledge and new ideas are necessary for a developing and well-functioning democratic society, the European Union declares education to be the fifth branch of power and grants it the following powers.
2. All educating powers herein granted shall be vested in the private educational institutions and the Teachers, Professors and Teachers' Debates of the Member States of the European Union.

Art. 132 Structure of Educating system

1. The education system shall comprise Kindergarten (Preschool), Primary-school, High-school and University.
2. In addition tutoring and talent nurturing shall be provided for children with special abilities, needs or interests.
3. The education shall happen in State educational institutions and Private educational institutions both respecting the basic educational policies.

Art. 133 Aim of Educating system

1. The aim of all stages of education, from kindergarten (preschool) to primary, high school and university, shall be to provide a comprehensive and integrated framework for developing individuals into well-rounded, socially conscious and ethical contributors to society. The stages of education aim to develop personal growth, emotional intelligence, and social abilities, as well as developing an inquisitive nature, while imparting virtues like kindness, collaboration, and respect for diverse cultures. Critical and logical thinking, problem-solving and a passion for learning are encouraged and students are equipped with the knowledge and skills to excel in their chosen fields. Additionally, at all educational levels, the emphasis is on developing personal moral and ethical values as well as encouraging civic engagement and advocating for social justice. The aim shall be to prepare students to deal with the challenges of an ever-changing world. The educational journey aims to enable individuals to make positive contributions to society, address complicated problems, and uphold the highest ethical principles by promoting creativity, cultural awareness, and a profound appreciation for lifelong learning.
2. Kindergarten or preschool education shall aim to create a nurturing environment for young children to foster their personal development, emotional intelligence, and social skills. It

shall focus on encouraging creativity, building character through values like kindness and cooperation, and instilling an early appreciation for diverse cultures. It shall introduce basic health and environmental awareness as well as incorporate the introduction of a foreign language to promote language acquisition skills at a young age, fostering linguistic diversity and cultural understanding. This comprehensive approach shall set the groundwork for well-rounded, socially conscious individuals with a strong foundation for future learning. Kindergarten shall aim to develop inquisitive and curious children.

3. Primary school education shall aim to play a vital role in laying the educational foundation for young learners. It shall aim to provide students with a comprehensive and well-rounded development, including intellectual growth through the promotion of critical and logical thinking, problem-solving skills, and a passion for learning, developing inquisitiveness and curiosity. Moreover, it shall emphasize moral and ethical development by promoting values such as honesty, responsibility, and empathy. Primary school also seeks to foster cultural competence through the exploration of literature, history, and the arts, enabling students to appreciate diverse cultural perspectives and fostering creativity. In addition to this, it equips students with life skills such as basic mathematics, literacy, effective communication, and informatics skills, and introduces foreign languages. Furthermore, it introduces scientific literacy and historical awareness, allowing students to better understand the world around them and learn from history's lessons. Primary school education is central to the development of future lifelong learners, ethical citizens, and well-rounded individuals.
4. The aim of High school (Secondary school) education shall be to build upon the foundational knowledge and inquisitiveness acquired in primary school and prepare students for the challenges of adulthood in a constantly evolving world. This is accomplished by pursuing a broader range of educational objectives. High school education focuses on cultivating global citizenship by enhancing students' awareness of international issues, diverse cultures, and their roles as responsible global citizens. Furthermore, it fosters civic engagement, encouraging active participation in communities and the democratic process. The High school shall strive to develop adaptability, innovation, creativity, and informatics skills, empowering students to think critically, solve complex problems, and contribute to progress in various fields. Moreover, it emphasizes empowerment by equipping students with the knowledge and skills to take control of their lives and make informed decisions, promoting personal and academic self-reliance. Emphasis is placed on equality and social justice, as students become advocates for a more just and equitable society. Sustainability education is also integrated, emphasising the importance of responsible environmental practices. High school education develops responsible, adaptable, innovative, and ethical individuals who are equipped to tackle the challenges of the contemporary world and make positive contributions to society. This is achieved through the teaching of a foreign language and a wide range of academic subjects, preparing students for a variety of future

prospects.

5. Universities shall serve as multifaceted institutions with a diverse range of aims and aspirations. Primarily, they are dedicated to providing a high-quality education, equipping students with the knowledge, critical and logical thinking skills, and practical expertise required to excel in their chosen fields. Beyond education, universities champion research, pushing the boundaries of human understanding across a wide spectrum of disciplines; from science and technology to the humanities and social sciences. They endeavour to make significant contributions to society through innovation, nurturing new discoveries, technologies, and solutions to complex global problems. Culturally, universities cultivate intellectual development, fostering environments where students engage with diverse ideas, perspectives and a global worldview. They aspire to act as beacons of community engagement and civic responsibility, connecting with their local communities and contributing positively to the broader societal fabric. Simultaneously, universities embrace the imperative of promoting diversity and inclusion, offering an environment where individuals from various backgrounds can flourish and learn together. They take on the role of promoting ethical and moral development, instilling values such as integrity, responsibility, and social conscience in their students. Health and wellness are also prioritized, with comprehensive healthcare and well-being services. Career placement and success are at the forefront for universities, preparing students for successful transitions to the workforce. Furthermore, they emphasize the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration to tackle complex challenges, and they are dedicated to maintaining high academic standards and promoting excellence in teaching and research. Universities also foster cultural exchange, and international understanding and advocate for social justice. Civic engagement is encouraged, motivating students and faculty to actively participate in addressing social issues and advocating for positive change. Continuous learning and lifelong education are supported through various programs and resources. Finally, universities commit to the ethical conduct of research and scholarship, ensuring research integrity and adherence to ethical standards. These multifaceted aims collectively make universities vital institutions that drive societal progress, personal growth, and the betterment of humanity.
6. Talent nurturing shall operate as a dynamic and inclusive process, striving to foster inquisitiveness, curiosity, creativity, critical and logical thinking, and individuality. The main objective is to empower students to embark on a journey of self-discovery and intellectual growth, encouraging them to seek answers and solutions through discovery-based learning methods. By providing students enough time to independently explore and uncover solutions, the focus shifts from competing against others to the joy of solving intriguing problems. This approach, rooted in inquiry and exploration, is driven by the belief that asking great questions is a gateway to intellectual growth. Through this method, we aim to nurture creativity and encourage students to forge their unique path, all while rec-

ognizing and fostering deeper connections within the knowledge they acquire. A critical aspect of this nurturing process is the collaborative element, as students work in groups, enabling them to share insights, challenge perspectives, and learn from one another's diverse experiences. In essence, talent nurturing strives to create an environment where individuality is celebrated, intellectual curiosity is ignited, and a profound appreciation for the art of questioning is developed, ultimately preparing students to excel not just academically, but in their lifelong pursuit of understanding the world around them.

Art. 134 Independence of Educating system

1. All schooling and education in the European Union shall be conducted independently, education shall prepare the students for the responsibility and challenges that shall fall on them once they reach the age of majority. As the fifth branch of power education shall be separated from the legislative, executive, judiciary and media powers.
2. Teachers shall have a large amount of autonomy and independence in teaching their subjects.
3. Educational institutions shall have total autonomy in conducting their affairs in so far as they abide by the educational policies devised by the Teachers' Debate of their Member State.

Art. 135 Financing of Educating system

1. The educational institutions shall put forward a budget plan based on the activities they need to fulfil and shall present it to the Teachers' Debate. Based on this the Legislature and the Teachers' Debate shall agree on an education budget.
2. The educational institutions shall be financed through a tax the amount of which shall be determined by the Legislature and the Teachers' Debate based on how much money the educational institutions need to function as required by the Constitution of the European Union and the law, this tax shall be paid by all the people.
3. The educational institutions must put forward a budget on how they propose to spend the money assigned to them. Their expenditure must be accessible to the public.
4. The legislature shall guarantee that the educational institutions have the necessary resources to function according to law and policies.

Art. 136 Compensation of teachers, professors and Members of the Teachers' Debate

1. The teachers, professors and Members of the Teachers' Debates of the European Union shall receive for their services a compensation. This compensation shall be ascertained by each Member State for their own educational area, however, all Member States must provide at least the average graduate income of the Member State. This does not apply to teachers and professors working in Private educational institutions only to those working in State educational institutions.

The Teachers' Debate

Art. 137 Structure and Members of the Teachers' Debate

1. The state educational institutions of each Member State shall be governed according to the policies of the Teachers' Debate of that Member State.
2. Each Member State shall have its own Teachers' Debate. The Debates shall, from time to time, assemble to discuss and achieve the harmonisation of European education.
3. The Teachers' Debates shall make their decisions according to the majority of the Debate Members.
4. The Teachers' Debates shall be a group of Directors who shall be appointed for a minimum of five years and a maximum of nine years. Half of the Members shall be appointed by the legislature while the other half shall be elected by the Directors of the State educational institutions. The Teachers' Debate shall consist of a minimum of twenty-five members.
5. No person may be removed from his post in the Teachers' Debates while his term lasts unless Impeached.
6. Employees of the state educational institutions work until their contract expires.

Art. 138 Appointment and Term of Members of the Teachers' Debate

1. The Teachers, Professors and to some extent the Students of each educational institution shall elect a Director for their educational institution, from amongst the Teachers or Professors of their educational institution. Half of the Members of the Teachers' Debate shall then be elected by the Directors of the State educational institutions, while the other half shall be elected by the legislature of the Member State; from amongst the Directors of the state educational institutions.

2. The term of the Members of the Teachers Debate shall be regulated by each Member State for its own Debate according to this Constitution.

Art. 139 Duties of the Teachers' Debate

1. It shall be the duty of the Teachers' Debate to make sure education is high quality and accessible to all. It shall make sure that each child upon reaching the age of majority is ready to take on the responsibilities of a citizen and is educated to the extent necessary to take over responsibility for themselves and the European Union.

Art. 140 Power of the Teachers' Debate

1. The consent of the Teachers' Debate shall be required for the adoption of any law governing or regulating education.
2. The legislature shall on request of the Teachers' Debate initiate bills governing and regulating education.
3. The Teachers' Debate shall make policies to govern and regulate education.
4. The Teachers' Debate can take recourse through the judiciary against the government and the legislature for their lack of action.

Offices of the European Union

Art. 141 The Office of Finance

1. The Office of Finance shall be responsible for managing the financial affairs of the European Union. Its primary function shall be to handle budgetary matters, revenue collection, and expenditure allocation in accordance with the Constitution, laws, and international treaties applicable to the European Union. The Office of Finance shall work towards ensuring the financial stability and economic prosperity of the European Union. It shall also oversee financial relations with Member States and international financial institutions.
2. The Office of Finance shall oversee customs and excise duties on imports and exports, safeguarding the European Union's interests in international trade.
3. The Office of Finance shall aim to ensure a fair and efficient taxation system while fostering economic growth throughout the European Union.
4. The Office of Finance shall manage the public debt of the European Union, ensuring responsible borrowing and effective debt management strategies.
5. The Office of Finance shall lead the European Union Treasury.
6. The Office of Finance shall cooperate with the European Central Bank to make the best out of European Union finances.
7. The President shall require the consent of the European Parliament for the appointment of the Commissioner of Finance.

Art. 142 The Office of Foreign Affairs

1. The Office of Foreign Affairs shall represent the interests of the European Union in international affairs. It shall be responsible for the development and implementation of foreign policy, in accordance with the Constitution, laws, and international treaties to which the European Union may be party. It shall negotiate and conclude treaties, agreements, and conventions on behalf of the European Union and its Member States. It shall maintain and develop friendly relations with foreign governments, international organizations, and non-governmental organizations for the promotion of peace, security, and economic development of the European Union. It shall be responsible for the implementation and enforcement of all international treaties and agreements to which the European Union may be party. In doing so it shall follow the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

2. The Office of Foreign Affairs shall maintain diplomatic and consular relations with foreign governments and international organizations. It shall provide assistance to the citizens of the European Union living or travelling abroad. To this end, it shall establish diplomatic and consular missions, including embassies, consulates, and other representative offices.
3. In all its activities the Office of Foreign Affairs shall represent the interests of the European Union and its Member States. It shall make sure that the Member States are represented on an international level.
4. The President shall require the consent of the European Parliament for the appointment of the Commissioner of Foreign Affairs.

Art. 143 The Office of Defence

1. The Office of Defence shall be responsible for the implementation of laws related to the defence and security of the European Union and its Member States. It shall develop and coordinate defence policies, oversee military capabilities, and ensure preparedness for potential threats to the European Union. The Office of Defence shall work towards fostering cooperation and coordination among Member States in defence matters. It shall maintain diplomatic relations with international defence organizations and handle crisis management related to security issues.
2. The Office of Defence shall lead the European Union Armed Forces. In doing so it shall leave the Institution sufficient autonomy to conduct its own affairs.
3. The President shall require the consent of the European Parliament for the appointment of the Commissioner of Defence.

Art. 144 The Office of Justice

1. The Office of Justice shall represent the interests of the European Union in legal matters, judicial affairs, and the administration of justice. It shall be responsible for the development and implementation of fair and just legal policies in accordance with the Constitution and the laws of the European Union.
2. The Office of Justice shall supervise the courts and the judiciary to ensure their independence and effectiveness in safeguarding the rights and freedoms of the citizens of the European Union. It shall furthermore enhance access to justice for all persons within the European Union.
3. The Office of Justice shall be responsible for consumer protection and the enforcement of laws that safeguard consumers from unfair business practices, ensuring a fair marketplace for economic growth.

4. The Office of Justice shall act in accordance with the guidelines of the President of the European Union.
5. The President shall require the consent of the European Parliament for the appointment of the Commissioner of Justice.

Art. 145 The Office of Interior

1. The Office of Interior shall be responsible for developing and implementing European Union laws related to ensuring the safety, security, and well-being of the citizens of the European Union. Its primary purpose shall be to maintain law and order, regulate immigration, and manage the European Union's internal affairs. It shall work towards creating a peaceful and harmonious society, where every citizen can live with dignity and respect. In doing so it shall follow the guidelines of the President of the European Union.
2. The Office of Interior shall maintain diplomatic relations with national entities, Member State governments, and internal organizations to promote harmonious cooperation and welfare among Member States within the European Union.
3. The Office of Interior shall lead Frontex and Europol. In doing so it shall leave the Institutions sufficient autonomy to conduct their own affairs.
4. The President shall require the consent of the European Parliament for the appointment of the Commissioner of the Interior.

Art. 146 The Office of Economics

1. The Office of Economics shall represent the economic interests of the European Union and its Member States. It shall be responsible for the development and implementation of policies related to trade, industry, commerce, and economic growth, under the Constitution and laws of the European Union.
2. The Office of Economics shall promote entrepreneurship, innovation, and competitiveness within the European Union and foster a business environment conducive to economic prosperity.
3. The Office of Economics shall cooperate with other countries and international organizations, facilitating trade agreements and promoting the economic interests of the European Union worldwide.
4. The Office of Economics shall act following the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

5. The President shall require the consent of the European Parliament for the appointment of the Commissioner of Economics.

Art. 147 The Office of Agriculture

1. The Office of Agriculture shall be responsible for developing European Union laws and ensuring that Member States execute European Union laws related to; farming, forestry, rural economic development, and food. It shall aim to meet the needs of commercial farming and livestock food production, promote agricultural trade and production, work to assure food safety and work to end hunger in the European Union and the world with great emphasis on sustainability. In doing so it shall follow the guidelines laid down by the President of the European Union.

Art. 148 The Office of Labour

1. The Office of Labour shall be responsible for developing European Union laws and ensuring that Member States execute European Union laws governing; occupational safety and health, wage and hour standards, unemployment benefits, reemployment services, and occasionally, economic statistics. In doing so it shall abide by the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

Art. 149 The Office of Health

1. The Office of Health shall be responsible for the developing of European Union laws, and ensuring that Member States execute European Union laws related to; health, health care systems, health insurance and the interests of patients. Its goal shall be to help people to live a long and healthy life. In doing so it shall respect the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

Art. 150 The Office of Infrastructure

1. Quality infrastructure is a necessary part of a welfare state. The European Union therefore creates the Office of Infrastructure to provide commodities and services essential to enable, sustain, or enhance social living conditions. The Office of Infrastructure shall be responsible for the developing of European Union laws and ensuring that Member States implement European Union laws governing; roads, water supply, sewers, electrical grids, and telecommunications. In working for the fulfillment of its goal it shall take special care of sustainability and respect the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

Art. 151 The Office of Transportation

1. The Office of Transportation shall be responsible for the development and coordination of laws and policies related to the European transportation system, with due regard for need, the environment, European defence and the guidelines of the President of the European Union. It shall also ensure Member States implement these laws.

Art. 152 The Office of Energy

1. The Office of Energy shall be responsible for the development and coordination of laws and policies related to the European Union and Member State energy systems, with due regard for need, the environment, European defence and the guidelines of the President of the European Union. It shall ensure that Member States implement these laws and policies.

Art. 153 The Office of Innovation, Research and Development

1. The European Union knowing that the future and welfare of Europe lies in innovation, research and development shall create the Office of Innovation, Research and Development. The Office of Innovation, Research and Development shall develop and ensure Member States implement European Union laws related to; new technologies, research, support of research and spreading of inventions. In doing so it shall follow the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

Art. 154 The Office of Education

1. The Office of Education shall develop laws and ensure laws related to education are implemented correctly. It shall support the Teacher's Debates in their duties and devise further ways to support and encourage education. In doing so it shall follow the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

Art. 155 The Office of Family Affairs

1. The Office of Family Affairs shall develop and ensure Member States execute laws related to family life; it shall make sure that the home environment is suitable for the care and upbringing of children. In doing so it shall follow the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

Art. 156 The Office of Seniors

1. The Office of Seniors shall create and ensure Member States implement European Union laws related to the everyday lives of seniors; it shall make sure seniors throughout the

European Union live a dignified life. In doing so it shall follow the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

Art. 157 The Office of Environment

1. The Office of Environment shall devise laws related to the environment, sustainability, preservation and upholding of nature. It shall ensure these laws are correctly executed by the Member States and shall take into account the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

Art. 158 The Office of Digitisation

1. The Office of Digitisation shall be responsible for the development of laws related to digital technology and the Internet. It shall aim to make these technologies easy to access and safe to use, as well as integrate them into everyday life. It shall ensure Member States execute these laws. In doing so it shall follow the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

Art. 159 The Office of Housing and Urban Development

1. The Office of Housing and Urban Development shall be responsible for the development of European Union laws related to housing. It shall ensure that Member States execute European Union laws related to housing, urban development, homelessness and affordability and sustainability of housing. In doing so it shall follow the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

Art. 160 The Office of Culture

1. The Office of Culture shall be responsible for the development of European Union laws related to; cultural heritage, cultural diversity and cultural preservation. It shall ascertain that Member States implement these laws correctly. In doing so it shall respect the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

Art. 161 The Office of Science

1. The Office of Science shall be responsible for the development of European laws related to; the encouragement of scientific research and spreading of scientific knowledge. It shall ascertain that Member States implement these laws correctly. In doing so it shall respect the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

Art. 162 The Office of Crisis Management

1. The Office of Crisis Management shall devise laws and policies related to crisis handling and prevention. It shall ensure that Member States implement these laws correctly. It shall aim to prepare the European Union for any crises where the everyday lives of the European people could be affected. In doing so it shall follow the guidelines of the President.
2. In the case of a crisis with the consent of two-thirds of the Members of the European Parliament and a double-qualified majority of the European Council the President of the European Union may give the Office of Crises Management temporary additional powers to help handle the crises.
3. The President shall require the consent of the European Parliament for the appointment of the Commissioner of Crisis Management.

Art. 163 The Office of Intelligence

1. The Office of Intelligence shall make sure the necessary information is on hand for the European Union and the Member States to function efficiently and effectively. In doing so it shall respect the guidelines of the President of the European Union and the Privacy of the people of the European Union.
2. The Office of Intelligence shall lead the European Intelligence Agency. In doing so it shall leave it sufficient autonomy to conduct its own affairs.
3. The President shall require the consent of the European Parliament for the appointment of the Commissioner of Intelligence.

Art. 164 The Office of Values and Transparency

1. The Office of Values and Transparency shall be responsible; for the spreading of European Values throughout the world, for the transparency and clarity of European Union and Member State activities, for legislation related to transparency as well as the sanctioning of Member States that fail to execute these laws in due time. In doing so it shall follow the guidelines of the President of the European Union.

Art. 165 The Office of Democracy and Demography

1. The Office of Democracy and Demography shall be responsible for the statistical mapping of demographic change and its impacts within the European Union and for creating laws related to a long-term vision for the European Union. It shall also ensure Member States execute these laws correctly. As well as ensuring that the democratic standards are upheld

equally in the whole of the European Union. In doing so it shall follow the guidelines of the president of the European Union.

Policies of the European Union

Education, Research and Cultural policies

Art. 166 European Education Area

1. The European Union and the Member States shall create a European Education Area.
2. The European Union and the Member States shall, within the scope of their powers, jointly ensure the high quality and accessibility of the European Education Area.
3. They shall coordinate their efforts and ensure their cooperation through joint administrative bodies and other measures.
4. They shall ensure in the fulfilment of their duties that general and vocational courses of study achieve equal recognition in society.
5. The European Union and its Member States shall make sure that the education systems of the different Member States are interoperable.

Art. 167 Kindergarten (Preschool)

1. The Teachers' Debate of the Member States are responsible for the system and functioning of Kindergarten (Preschool).
2. They shall ensure that a high-quality Kindergarten (Preschool) is available to all children and especially to children in great need.
3. The Teachers' Debates shall participate in the drafting of European Union legislation on Preschool education that affects their responsibilities, and special account shall be taken of their opinions.

Art. 168 School education

1. The Teachers' Debate of the Member States are responsible for the system and functioning of school education.
2. They shall ensure the provision of an adequate basic education that is available to all children. Basic education is mandatory and is managed or supervised by the Teacher's Debates. At state schools, it is free of charge.
3. The Teachers' Debates shall ensure that adequate special needs education is provided to all children and young people with disabilities.

4. Where harmonisation of school education is not achieved using coordination in the areas of school entry age and compulsory school attendance, the duration and objectives of levels of education, and the transition from one level to another, as well as the recognition of qualifications, the Presidents of the Teachers' Debates of the Member States shall issue regulations to achieve such harmonisation.
5. The Member States may regulate the start of the school year.
6. The Teachers' Debates shall participate in the drafting of European Union legislation on school education that affects their responsibilities, and special account shall be taken of their opinions.

Art. 169 Vocational and professional education and training

1. The Teachers' Debates shall issue regulations on vocational and professional education and training.
2. They shall encourage the provision of a diverse and accessible range of courses in vocational and professional education and training.

Art. 170 Higher education institutions

1. The Teachers' Debates shall manage the Institutes of Technology. They may establish, take over or manage additional universities and other higher education institutions.
2. They shall support the universities and shall make financial contributions to other higher education institutions that they recognise.
3. The European Union and the Teachers' Debates are jointly responsible for the coordination and guarantee of quality in European higher education. In fulfilling this responsibility, they shall take account of the autonomy of the universities and the various bodies responsible for them and ensure the equal treatment of institutions with the same functions.
4. To fulfil their duties, the European Union and the Teachers' Debates shall enter into agreements and delegate certain powers to joint administrative authorities. The law shall regulate the powers that may be delegated, and determine the principles governing the organisation of and procedures for coordination.

Art. 171 Continuing education and training

1. The European Union shall specify principles governing continuing education and training with the help of the Teachers' Debates.

2. It may promote continuing education and training.
3. The law shall specify the fields of and the criteria for such promotion.

Art. 172 Education grants

1. The European Union may contribute to Member State expenditure on grants provided to students at universities and higher education institutions. It may encourage the inter-Member State harmonisation of education grants and lay down principles for the payment of education grants.
2. It may also supplement Member State measures while preserving Member State autonomy in education matters by taking its own measures to promote education.

Art. 173 Encouragement and Talent nurturing of children and young people

1. In fulfilling their duties, the Teachers' Debate, the European Union and the Member States shall take account of the special needs of children and young people to receive encouragement and protection.
2. The European Union, the Member States and the Teachers' Debate shall make sure that talented children and young people get the chance to nurture their talent with the help of talent-nurturing programs.
3. The European Union may supplement Member State measures by supporting extra-curricular work with children and young people.

Art. 174 Musical education

1. The European Union and the Member States shall encourage musical education, in particular, that of children and young people.
2. The Teachers' Debate shall endeavour within the scope of its powers to ensure high-quality music teaching in schools.
3. In consultation with the Teachers' Debates of the Member States, the European Union shall set out principles to help young people engage in musical activities and to encourage musically gifted persons.

Art. 175 Sport

1. The European Union shall encourage sport, and in particular education in sport.
2. The Teachers' Debates shall operate sports schools.
3. The European Union may issue regulations on sports for young people and declare the teaching of sports in schools to be compulsory.

Art. 176 Culture

1. Cultural matters are a Member State's responsibility.
2. The European Union may support cultural activities of European interest as well as art and music, in particular in the field of education.
3. In the fulfilment of its duties, it shall take account of the cultural and linguistic diversity of the Union.
4. The Teachers' Debates of the Member States shall regulate the education of culture.

Art. 177 Languages

1. The Member States shall decide on their official languages. To preserve harmony between linguistic communities, the Member States shall respect the traditional territorial distribution of languages and take account of indigenous linguistic minorities.
2. The European Union and the Member States shall encourage understanding and exchange between the linguistic communities.
3. The European Union shall support the multilingual Member States in the fulfilment of their special duties.
4. The Teachers' Debates shall make sure that the students learn foreign languages.

Art. 178 Science

1. The European Union and the Member States shall promote science.
2. The Teachers' Debate shall make sure that students receive adequate education in sciences.

Art. 179 Mathematics

1. The European Union and the Member States shall promote mathematics.
2. The Teachers' Debate shall make sure that students receive adequate education in mathematics.

Art. 180 Cinema

1. The European Union may encourage European film production and film culture.
2. It may issue regulations to promote the diversity and the quality of the cinematographic works that are offered.

Art. 181 Statistics

1. The European Union shall compile the necessary statistical data on the status and trends in the population, the economy, society, education, research, the land and the environment in Europe.
2. It may issue regulations on the harmonisation and maintenance of official registers to reduce the cost of compiling data.

Art. 182 Research

1. The European Union shall promote scientific research and innovation.
2. It may make its support conditional in particular on quality assurance and coordination being guaranteed.
3. The European Union and the Member States may establish, take over or run research institutes.

Art. 183 Church and state

1. The European Union and the Member States shall make sure that the church and the state are separated from one another.
2. The European Union and the Member States may within the scope of their powers take measures to preserve public peace between the members of different religious communities.

Environment and Spatial Planning policies

Art. 184 Sustainable development and protection of the environment

1. The European Union and the Member States shall endeavour to achieve a balanced and sustainable relationship between nature and its capacity to renew itself and the demands placed on it by the population.
2. The European Union shall legislate on the protection of the population and its natural environment against damage or nuisance.
3. It shall ensure that such damage or nuisance is avoided. The costs of avoiding or eliminating such damage or nuisance are borne by those responsible for causing it.
4. The Member States are responsible for the implementation of the relevant European Union regulations, except where the law reserves this duty for the European Union.

Art. 185 Spatial planning

1. The European Union shall lay down principles on spatial planning. These principles are binding on the Member States and serve to ensure the appropriate and economic use of the land and its properly ordered settlement.
2. The European Union shall encourage and coordinate the efforts of the Member States and shall cooperate with them.
3. The European Union and the Member States shall take account of the requirements of spatial planning in fulfilling their duties.

Art. 186 European Land Survey

1. The European Land Survey is the responsibility of the European Union.
2. The European Union shall issue regulations on official surveying.
3. It may issue regulations on the harmonisation of official information relating to the land.

Art. 187 Water

1. The European Union shall within the scope of its powers ensure the economic use and the protection of water resources and provide protection against the harmful effects of water.

2. It shall lay down principles on the conservation and exploitation of water resources, the use of water for the production of energy and cooling purposes, as well as on other measures affecting the water cycle.
3. It shall legislate on water protection, on ensuring appropriate residual flow, on hydraulic engineering and the safety of dams, and on measures that influence precipitation.
4. The Member States shall manage their water resources. They may levy charges for the use of water, subject to the limits imposed by European Union legislation. The European Union has the right to use water for its transport operations subject to payment of a charge and compensation.
5. The European Union, in consultation with the Member States concerned, shall decide on rights to international water resources and the charges for them. If Member States are unable to agree on rights to inter-Member State water resources, the European Union shall decide.
6. The European Union shall take account of the concerns of the Member State where the water originates in fulfilling its duties.

Art. 188 Forests

1. The European Union shall ensure that the forests can fulfil their protective, commercial and public amenity functions.
2. It shall lay down principles on the protection of the forests.
3. It shall encourage measures for the conservation of the forests.

Art. 189 Protection of natural and cultural heritage

1. The protection of natural and cultural heritage is the responsibility of the Member States.
2. In the fulfilment of its duties, the European Union shall take account of concerns for the protection of natural and cultural heritage. It shall protect the countryside and places of architectural, historical, natural or cultural interest; it shall preserve such places intact if required to do so in the public interest.
3. It may support efforts made for the protection of natural and cultural heritage and acquire or preserve properties of national importance by contract or through compulsory purchase.
4. It shall legislate on the protection of animal and plant life and the preservation of their natural habitats and their diversity. It shall protect endangered species from extinction.

5. Moors and wetlands of special beauty and national importance shall be preserved. No buildings may be built on them and no changes may be made to the land, except for the construction of facilities that serve the protection of the moors or wetlands or their continued use for agricultural purposes.
6. The Member States shall create their own protective land areas. The European Union may assist them in the maintenance of such lands.

Art. 190 Fishing and hunting

1. The European Union shall lay down principles on fishing and hunting and in particular on the preservation of the diversity of fish species, wild mammals, reptiles and birds.

Art. 191 Protection of animals

1. The European Union shall legislate on the protection of animals.
2. It shall in particular regulate:
 - (a) the keeping and care of animals;
 - (b) experiments on animals and procedures carried out on living animals;
 - (c) the use of animals;
 - (d) the import of animals and animal products;
 - (e) the trade in animals and the transport of animals;
 - (f) the killing of animals.
3. The enforcement of the regulations is the responsibility of the Member States, except where the law reserves this to the European Union.

Public Construction Works and Transport policies

Art. 192 Public Construction Works

1. The European Union may in the interests of the union as a whole or a large part of it carry out and operate public construction works, or provide support for such construction works.

Art. 193 Public transport

1. The European Union and the Member States shall ensure that an adequate range of public transport services are provided on rail, roads and by water in all regions of the union. In doing so, an appropriate account must be taken of the interests of rail freight transport.
2. The costs of public transport shall be covered by the Member States and to an appropriate extent by the prices paid by users.

Art. 194 Road transport and road infrastructure

1. The European Union shall legislate on road transport, however, Member States may create stricter rules within their own territory.
2. The European Union shall exercise oversight over roads of union importance; it may decide which transit roads must remain open to traffic.
3. Public roads may be used free of charge. The Member States may authorise exceptions in special cases.
4. The European Union shall help the Member States to ensure that there is adequate road infrastructure in the whole of their territory.
5. The Member States shall ensure the construction of a network of national highways and guarantee that they remain usable. They shall construct, operate and maintain the national highways. They shall bear the costs thereof. They may assign this task wholly or partly to public or private bodies or combined public-private bodies. The European Union may support the Member States to meet their guarantee.

Art. 195 Railways and railway infrastructure

1. The Member States shall be responsible for the regulation and financing of their own railways.
2. The European Union may assist them in meeting their guarantee and finance the construction of high-speed or inter-Member State railways.

Art. 196 Other modes of Transport

1. The legislation on shipping, aviation and space travel is the responsibility of the European Union.

Art. 197 Footpaths, hiking trails and cycle paths

1. The European Union shall lay down principles concerning the network of footpaths, hiking trails and cycle paths.
2. It may support and coordinate measures by the Member States and third parties to construct and maintain such networks and to provide information about them. In doing so, it shall respect the powers of the Member States.
3. It shall take account of these networks in the fulfilment of its duties. It shall replace paths and trails that it has to close.

Energy and Communications policies

Art. 198 Energy policy

1. Within the scope of their powers, the European Union and the Member States shall endeavour to ensure a sufficient, diverse, safe, economic and environmentally sustainable energy supply as well as the economic and efficient use of energy.
2. The European Union shall legislate on the use of energy by installations, vehicles and appliances, however, Member States may create stricter legislation in their own territory. The European Union and the Member States shall encourage the development of energy technologies, in particular in the fields of saving energy and renewable energy sources.
3. The Member States shall be responsible for the development and maintenance of their energy supplies.
4. The European Union shall defend all the Member States from energy blackouts and supply-chain disruptions and their consequences in so far as its power allows it.
5. The European Union shall take into account in its energy policy the efforts made by the Member States, the communes and the business community; it shall take account of the conditions in the individual regions of the Member States and the limitations of what is economically feasible.

Art. 199 Internal Energy Market

1. The European Union shall create the Internal Energy Market, and it shall be responsible for legislation in the field of the Internal Energy Market.
2. The European Union shall make sure that the Internal Energy Market is:
 - (a) free from numerous obstacles and trade barriers;

- (b) approximate in tax and pricing policies and measures in respect of norms and standards;
 - (c) environment friendly and passes the necessary safety regulations;
 - (d) fairly accessible and has a high level of consumer protection;
 - (e) interconnected and has adequate generation capacity.
3. The Member States shall cooperate with the European Union in the creation and development of the Internal Energy Market.
 4. The European Union and the affected Member States shall finance Internal Energy Market projects jointly.

Art. 200 International Energy policies

1. The European Union shall make contracts with foreign energy suppliers in the name and the interest of all the Member States.
2. The Member States may request contracts with special foreign states however they may not sign such contracts.
3. The European Union shall co-finance the ascertainments of the contracts with the Member States.

Art. 201 Renewable energy

1. The European Union shall establish principles for the use of renewable energy. It may make legislation in the field of renewable energy, however, any Member State may create stricter legislation within its own territory.

Art. 202 Nuclear energy

1. The European Union shall be responsible for legislation in the field of nuclear energy, however, any Member State may create stricter legislation within its own territory.

Art. 203 Postal services

1. The Member States shall be responsible for postal services.
2. The Member States shall ensure the adequate, universal and reasonably priced provision of postal services in all regions of their territory. The rates shall be fixed according to standard principles.

3. The European Union and the Member States shall make sure that inter-Member State postal services meet the same standards as Member State postal services.
4. The European Union shall create a European postal market open to competition. The European Union shall have the right to regulate this market.

Art. 204 Telecommunications services

1. The European Union shall be responsible for legislation on telecommunications.
2. The European Union and the Member States shall create a high quality consumer protective European telecommunications market.

Housing, Employment, Social Security and Health policies

Art. 205 Real estate ownership and construction

1. The European Union and the Member States shall encourage the construction of housing, the acquisition of the ownership of apartments and houses for the personal use of private individuals, as well as the activities of developers and organisations involved in the construction of public utility housing.
2. They shall encourage in particular the acquisition and development of land for the construction of housing, increased efficiency in construction and the reduction of construction and housing costs.
3. They may legislate on the development of land for housing construction and on increasing the efficiency of construction.
4. In doing so, they shall take particular account of the interests of families, elderly persons, persons on low incomes and persons with disabilities.

Art. 206 Proprietor and tenant

1. The Member States shall legislate against abuses in tenancy matters, and in particular against unfair rents, as well as on the procedure for challenging unlawfully terminated leases and the limited extension of leases.
2. They may legislate to declare framework leases to be generally applicable. Such leases may be declared generally applicable only if they take appropriate account of the justified

interests of minorities and regional particularities, and respect the principle of equality before the law.

3. The European Union may make legislation in cases where the coordination of the Member State laws is necessary for the functioning of the European Union housing market.

Art. 207 Employment

1. The European Union may legislate on:
 - (a) protection of employees;
 - (b) relations between employer and employee, and in particular on common regulations on operational and professional matters;
 - (c) recruitment services;
 - (d) the declaration of collective employment agreements to be generally applicable.
2. Collective employment agreements may be declared generally applicable only if they take appropriate account of the justified interests of minorities and regional particularities, and they respect the principle of equality before the law and the right to form professional associations.
3. Europe Day on May 9th is the National Day of the European Union. In terms of employment law, it is regarded as equivalent to a Sunday, with equivalent rights to pay.

Art. 208 Old-age, Survivors and Disability Insurance

1. The European Union shall take measures to ensure adequate financial provision for the elderly, surviving spouses and children, and persons with disabilities. It shall ensure that this financial provision is fulfilled at all times.
2. The European Union and the Member States shall legislate on the Old-age, Survivors and Disability Insurance.
3. In doing so they shall comply with the following principles:
 - (a) the insurance is compulsory;
 - (b) it provides cash and non-cash benefits;
 - (c) pensions must be sufficient to cover basic living expenses adequately;
 - (d) pensions must as a minimum be adjusted in line with price trends.

4. The insurance shall be funded in each Member State through contributions from those insured, whereby employers must pay one-half of the contributions payable by their employees. The European Union may provide subsidies to support the Member States.
5. The European Union and the Member States shall promote the rehabilitation of people eligible for disability benefits.

Art. 209 Occupational pension

1. The European Union shall set principles for occupational pensions.
2. In doing so, it shall adhere to the following:
 - (a) The occupational pension scheme, together with the Old-age, Survivors and Disability Insurance, enables the insured person to maintain his or her previous lifestyle in an appropriate manner.
 - (b) The occupational pension scheme is compulsory for employees; the law may provide for exceptions.
 - (c) Employers shall insure their employees with a pension institution; if required, the European Union shall make it possible for employees to be insured with a European Union pension institution.
 - (d) Self-employed persons may insure themselves on a voluntary basis with a pension institution.
 - (e) For specific groups of self-employed persons, the European Union may declare the occupational pension scheme to be compulsory, either in general terms or for individual risks only.
3. The occupation pension scheme shall be funded from the contributions of those insured, whereby employers must pay a minimum of one-half of the contributions of their employees.
4. The Member States shall have total autonomy in the legislation and functioning of their occupational pensions in so far as they abide by the principles of the European Union.

Art. 210 Unemployment insurance

1. The European Union shall set principles for unemployment insurance.
2. In doing so it shall adhere to the following:
 - (a) The insurance guarantees appropriate compensation for loss of earnings and supports measures to prevent and combat unemployment;

- (b) The insurance is compulsory for employees; the law may provide for exceptions;
 - (c) Self-employed persons may insure themselves voluntarily.
3. The insurance shall be funded by the contributions from those insured, whereby one-half of the contributions of employees shall be paid by their employers.
 4. The Member States shall have total autonomy in the legislation and functioning of their unemployment insurance in so far as they abide by the principles of the European Union.

Art. 211 Child allowances

1. The Member States shall take account of the needs of their families, they may support measures for the protection of families.
2. They may issue regulations on child allowances and operate a family allowances compensation fund.
3. They shall establish a maternity insurance scheme. They may also require persons who cannot benefit from that insurance to make contributions.
4. The Member States must take into account the principles of the European Union.
5. The European Union may set principles for Child allowances.

Art. 212 Health and accident insurance

1. The European Union shall legislate on health and accident insurance.
2. It may declare health and accident insurance to be compulsory in general for the entire population.

Art. 213 Primary medical care and health protection

1. The Member States shall within the scope of their powers ensure the adequate provision of high-quality primary medical care that is accessible to all. They shall recognise and promote family medicine as an essential component of primary care. The European Union shall support the Member States in the fulfilment of their duty.
2. The European Union may legislate on:
 - (a) basic and continuing education and training for family medicine professions and the requirements for practising these professions;
 - (b) appropriate remuneration for family medicine services.

3. The European Union and the Member States shall, within the limits of their powers, take measures for the protection of health.
4. The European Union shall legislate on:
 - (a) the use of foodstuffs as well as therapeutic products, narcotics, organisms, chemicals and items that may be dangerous to health;
 - (b) the combating of communicable, widespread or particularly dangerous human and animal diseases;
 - (c) protection against ionising radiation.

Art. 214 Research on human beings

1. The European Union shall legislate on research on human beings, it shall make sure that their dignity and privacy are protected. In doing so, it shall preserve the freedom to conduct research and shall take account of the importance of research to health and society.
2. The European Union, concerning biological and medical research involving human beings, shall adhere to the following principles:
 - (a) It is a requirement for any research project that the participants or their legal representatives have given their informed consent. A refusal is binding in every case.
 - (b) The risks and stress for the participants must not be disproportionate to the benefits of the research project.
 - (c) A research project involving persons lacking the capacity to consent may be conducted only if findings of equal value cannot be obtained from research involving persons who have the capacity to consent. If the research project is not expected to bring any immediate benefit to the persons lacking the capacity to consent, the risks and stress must be minimal.
 - (d) An independent assessment of the research project must have determined that the safety of the participants is guaranteed.

Art. 215 Reproductive medicine and gene technology

1. Human beings and their environment shall be protected against the misuse of reproductive medicine and gene technology.
2. The European Union shall ensure the protection of human dignity, privacy and the family and shall adhere in particular to the following principles in the question of gene technology:

- (a) All people shall be protected from discrimination on the grounds of genetic material.
 - (b) The genetic material of a person may be analysed, registered or made public only with the consent of the person concerned.
 - (c) Every person shall have access to data relating to their ancestry.
 - (d) The trade in human reproductive material and products obtained from embryos is prohibited.
 - (e) The donation of embryos and all forms of surrogate motherhood is unlawful.
3. The European Union shall make sure that in legislation on human gene technology, none of its laws violate any of the basic rights.
 4. The European Union shall legislate on the use of reproductive and genetic material from animals, plants and other organisms. In doing so, it shall take account of the dignity of living beings as well as the safety of human beings, animals and the environment, and shall protect the genetic diversity of animal and plant species.

Art. 216 Transplant medicine

1. The European Union shall legislate in the field of organ, tissue and cell transplants. In doing so, it shall ensure the protection of human dignity, privacy and health.
2. It shall in particular lay down criteria for the fair allocation of organs.
3. Any donation of human organs, tissue and cells must be free of charge. The trade-in human organs is prohibited and shall be severely punished.

Art. 217 Cloning of humans

1. The European Union shall legislate on the use of human genetic material. It shall adhere to the guarantees in the Constitution of the European Union.
2. The European Union and the Member States shall guarantee that all people are defended from:
 - (a) The introduction of non-human reproductive and genetic material into human reproductive material or the combination of non-human reproductive and genetic material with human reproductive material.
 - (b) The modification of their genetic material.
3. The procedures for medically-assisted reproduction may be used only if infertility or the risk of transmitting a serious illness cannot otherwise be overcome, but not in order to

conceive a child with specific characteristics or to further research; the fertilisation of human egg cells outside a woman's body is permitted only under the conditions laid down by the law; no more human egg cells may be developed into embryos outside a woman's body than are required for medically-assisted reproduction.

Digital policies

Art. 218 Digital Market

1. The European Union shall take all necessary measures to create a unified, free and fair European Union Digital Market.
2. It shall address the challenges posed by digital services, which encompass a wide range of online platforms and services, from social networks to online marketplaces. It shall fight the exchange of illegal goods and content online, as well as the spread of disinformation through manipulative algorithms. It shall aim to avert monopolies in the digital market. It shall protect fundamental rights, establish fair governance, and promote innovation and competitiveness in the digital market by applying consistent rules across the European Union.
3. The European Union shall legislate on the digital market and digital services.

Art. 219 Personal Data and Data Storage

1. The European Union shall ensure the protection of citizens' basic rights and freedoms regarding the processing of their personal data. It shall aim to establish clear principles, rules, and safeguards for the handling of personal data, promoting transparency, accountability, and respect for privacy.
2. The European Union shall legislate on the handling and storage of the Data of its citizens.
3. The Data of European Union citizens shall be stored and processed on servers within the territory of the European Union.

Art. 220 Artificial Intelligence

1. The aim of an AI regulating law shall be to establish a comprehensive and balanced framework that promotes the ethical and responsible development, deployment, and use of artificial intelligence systems.
2. The European Union shall prioritize the development of AI systems that adhere to ethical principles, such as fairness, transparency, accountability, and privacy. It shall ensure

that AI systems do not perpetuate biases, discriminate against individuals or groups, or infringe upon fundamental rights.

3. The European Union shall emphasize the safety and security of AI systems. It shall require testing, risk assessment, and mitigation strategies to minimize potential harms or risks posed by AI technologies. This may include measures to prevent malicious use, protect against cyber threats, and establish standards for system reliability.
4. The European Union shall promote transparency and explainability of AI systems. It shall mandate that AI algorithms and decision-making processes are open to scrutiny, with clear explanations provided for any decisions made by AI systems. This would help build trust and enable individuals to understand how and why certain decisions are made.
5. The European Union shall safeguard individuals' personal data and privacy rights in the context of AI systems. It shall establish guidelines for the collection, use, storage, and sharing of data, ensuring that consent is obtained, and data is handled securely. Additionally, it shall address issues related to data anonymization and de-identification to protect privacy.
6. The European Union shall define clear lines of accountability and liability for AI systems. It shall specify the roles and responsibilities of developers, manufacturers, operators, and users of AI systems in case of any adverse consequences. This would encourage responsible behaviour and provide recourse for those affected by AI-related incidents.
7. Given the global nature of AI, the European Union shall encourage international cooperation and collaboration. It shall promote the development of common standards, best practices, and regulatory frameworks to ensure harmonization and facilitate the safe and ethical deployment of AI systems across borders.
8. The European Union shall establish mechanisms for ongoing monitoring and adaptation to keep pace with the rapidly evolving AI landscape. It shall create regulatory bodies or agencies responsible for overseeing AI development, conducting audits, and updating regulations as needed.
9. The European Union shall legislate on AI to strike a balance between promoting innovation and societal benefits while mitigating potential risks and ensuring that AI systems are developed and deployed responsibly, ethically, and in the best interests of humanity.

Economic policies

Art. 221 Economic Freedom and Order

1. The European Union may legislate on the exercise of private economic activity.

2. The European Union and the Member States shall respect the principle of economic freedom, they shall safeguard the interests of the European economy and, together with the private sector of the economy, contribute to the welfare and economic security of the population.
3. The European Union and the Member States shall strive to create favourable conditions for the private sector of the economy.
4. Derogations from the principle of economic freedom, in particular measures against competition, shall be allowed only if foreseen by the Constitution of the European Union or based on Member State monopolies.

Art. 222 European Economic Area

1. The European Union shall take all necessary measures to create a unified European Union Economic Area.

Art. 223 Competition Policy

1. The European Union shall legislate to fight against economically or socially damaging effects of cartels and other restrictions of competition.
2. The European Union shall take measures:
 - (a) to prevent abuses in price fixing by enterprises and organizations of private and public law enjoying a dominant position on the market;
 - (b) against unfair competition.
3. The European Union shall make sure that no Member State shall suffer from economically or socially damaging effects of cartels and other restrictions of competition.
4. The European Union shall make sure that public procurements are free, competitive, fair and equal.

Art. 224 Consumer Protection

1. The European Union shall take measures for consumer protection.
2. It shall legislate on the remedies available to consumer organizations. In the field of European Union legislation against unfair competition, these organizations shall have the same rights as professional and economic associations.

Art. 225 Monetary Policy

1. Money and currency shall be European Union matters. The European Union shall have the exclusive right to coin money and to issue bank notes.
2. The European Central Bank shall be responsible for the monetary policy of the European Union, it shall conduct its duty independently and according to the general interest of the union; it shall be administered with the cooperation and under the supervision of the European Union.
3. The European Central Bank shall create sufficient monetary reserves from its profits; part of these reserves shall be held in gold.
4. At least two-thirds of the net profits of the European Central Bank shall be credited to the Member States.

Art. 226 Foreign Trade

1. The European Union shall safeguard abroad the interests of the European economy.
2. In special cases, the European Union may take measures to protect the domestic economy. It may, if necessary, temporarily depart from the principle of economic freedom.

Art. 227 Crucial Goods and Services

1. The European Union shall ensure the union's supply of essential goods and services in case of threats of military or economic war, or of severe shortages which the economy cannot counteract by itself. It shall take provisional measures.
2. The European Union may, if necessary, temporarily depart from the principle of economic freedom.

Art. 228 Economic Development

1. The European Union shall take measures to ensure balanced economic development and, in particular, to prevent and fight unemployment and inflation in doing so it shall collaborate with the Member States and economic circles.
2. The European Union may in the fields of credit and currency, in foreign trade and public finance, if necessary, depart from the principle of economic freedom.
3. The European Union may support economically threatened regions and promote branches of the economy and professions if the measures of self-help that can reasonably be expected

are insufficient to ensure their existence. It may, if necessary, temporarily depart from the principle of economic freedom.

4. In their budgetary policy, the European Union, the Member States and Municipalities shall take into account the economic development.
5. The European Union and the Member States may, to stabilize the economy, temporarily levy surcharges, or grant rebates on taxes and dues. The accumulated funds shall be frozen; after their release, direct surcharges shall be individually reimbursed, and indirect surcharges shall be used to grant rebates or to create employment in addition they may oblige businesses to accumulate reserves for the creation of employment; for this purpose, they shall grant tax privileges. After the release of the reserves, the businesses shall be free to decide how to use them within the purposes prescribed by statute.

Art. 229 Agriculture

1. The European Union shall ensure that agriculture contributes substantially by way of sustainable and market-oriented production:
 - (a) to the secure appropriate supply of the population;
 - (b) to the conservation of national resources and the upkeep of rural scenery;
 - (c) to decentralized in-habitation of the country.
2. In addition to the measures of self-help that may reasonably be expected from agriculture and, if necessary, in derogation of the principle of economic freedom, the European Union shall promote farms cultivating the land.
3. The European Union shall conceive the measures in such a way that agriculture may fulfil its multiple functions. Its powers and tasks shall particularly be the following:
 - (a) It shall complement agricultural revenues by direct payments, to secure fair and adequate remuneration for the services rendered, provided that compliance with ecological requirements is proven;
 - (b) It shall promote, by way of economic incentives, forms of production that are particularly close to nature and friendly to the environment and the animals;
 - (c) It shall legislate on the declaration of origin, quality, production and processing methods for foodstuffs;
 - (d) It shall protect the environment against pollution due to excessive use of fertilizers, chemicals and other auxiliary substances;
 - (e) It may encourage agricultural research, counseling, and education, and subsidize investments;

- (f) It may legislate on the consolidation of rural property.
- 4. To these ends the European Union shall invest dedicated funds from the agricultural field and general European Union funds.

Art. 230 Weapons

1. The European Union shall legislate on the misuse of weapons, associated equipment, and ammunition, however, Member States may create stricter rules in so far as they do not violate the European Union Law.
2. It shall legislate on the production, acquisition, distribution, importation, exportation, and transit of military material in doing so it shall make sure that it does not violate the security of any Member State.

The Foreign Affairs of the European Union

Foreign Affairs

Art. 231 The basis of Foreign Affairs

1. Foreign Affairs shall be conducted by the European Union.
2. The European Union shall do its utmost to preserve the independence and autonomy of its Member States and their welfare; it shall, in particular, contribute to alleviating need and poverty in the world, and to promote respect for human rights, democracy, the peaceful coexistence of nations, and the preservation of natural resources.
3. The European Union shall take into consideration the powers of the Member States, and shall protect their interests in the execution of Foreign Affairs.
4. If the powers of the Member States are affected the Member States shall participate in the international negotiations appropriately.

Art. 232 Member State Foreign Affairs

1. After the endorsement of the European Union, Member States may conduct special treaties with neighbouring States. So long as these treaties fall within their powers and so long as these treaties do not offend the interests of the European Union or any other Member State.

Diplomatic and Consular representation

Art. 233 Diplomatic and Consular representation

1. The Member States shall uphold diplomatic and consular representation in foreign countries to defend the rights of their nationals as well as the nationals of other European Union Member States, in doing so they shall always take account of the policies of the European Union and its Member States and shall act accordingly.
2. The European Union shall support them in their task.
3. The Member States may appoint their own Ambassadors to foreign states.

Residence of non-European Union Citizens

Art. 234 Residence of Foreigners

1. The European Union shall legislate on immigration, emigration, residence and domicile of foreigners, and on granting asylum, in doing so it shall make sure that no Member State suffers any disadvantage.
2. Foreigners who endanger the European Union and its Member States' security may be removed from the European Union by force.
3. Asylum applicants shall wait at the European Union borders while their applications are processed. Only if and once granted asylum are they free to enter the European Union.
4. Before being considered for asylum, individuals must take the following Oath: "I do solemnly swear (or affirm) that I will contribute to the well-being of the European people, protect them from harm, defend and obey the Constitution and laws of the European Union, act honestly, and do my utmost to integrate into European society." Those who refuse to take the oath may not be granted asylum.
5. The European Union shall aim to process asylum applications as quickly as possible. It shall only grant asylum to as many people as financially and culturally possible. When granting asylum the European Union shall give priority to refugees who are minors, who are educated, who have knowledge of a European language or who belong to a family with minors.
6. The European Union may require refugees to do community work if they are otherwise unemployed.
7. Refugees who endanger or reject the democratic basic order of the European Union may be removed from the European Union immediately.

The Finances of the European Union

Art. 235 Financial management

1. The European Union and the Member States shall maintain their income and expenditure in balance over time.
2. The ceiling for total expenditure that is to be approved in the budget is based on the expected income after taking account of the economic situation.
3. Exceptional financial requirements may justifying an appropriate increase in the ceiling in terms of paragraph 2. The European Congress shall legislate on any increase.
4. If the total expenditure of the European Union or its Member States exceeds the ceiling in terms of paragraphs 2 or 3, compensation for this additional expenditure shall be made in subsequent years.
5. The European Union shall legislate on further details.

Art. 236 Principles of taxation

1. The main structural features of any tax, in particular the persons liable to pay the tax, the purpose of the tax and its assessment, shall be laid down by law.
2. To the extent permitted by the nature of the tax, the principles of universality and uniformity of taxation as well as the principle of taxation according to ability to pay shall be applied.
3. The European Union shall ensure that no person or legal entity shall be taxed twice by different Member States on the same income or property.

Art. 237 Functioning of taxation

1. Within their own jurisdiction the laying and collection of taxes shall be the exclusive right and duty of the Member States.
2. The Member States shall legislate on the scope purpose and rate of taxation within their own jurisdiction; within the boundaries set by the European Union.
3. The European Union may legislate on the scope and purpose of taxation; it may set a minimum tax rate with the aim of harmonising the European tax system.

Art. 238 Customs duties

1. The European Union shall legislate on the questions of Customs duties.
2. The Customs duties of the European Union shall be collected in each Member State by the Customs authority thereof and shall then be paid into the European Union Treasury. To this end, the European Union may create a European Customs authority to assist the Member States in the fulfilment of their task.

Art. 239 Distribution of tax revenue

1. All tax revenue shall be allocated to the Member States except the part of the revenue bindingly committed to the Budget of the European Union as defined in Art. 240. Such revenue shall be forthwith paid into the Treasury of the European Union.
2. Such financing shall be proportionate to the Gross Domestic Product of each Member State, however, in special cases depending on the affair it may be proportionate to the population of the Member States.
3. The European Congress shall legislate on the contributions of the Member States.

Art. 240 Apportionment of expenditures

1. The European Union and its Member States shall maintain their government budgetary positions with an annual deficit not exceeding 3% of their Gross Domestic Product (GDP) unless they qualify for temporary derogations under specific circumstances.
2. If a Member State violates the deficit criteria, the Office of Finance can initiate recommendations to the Member State to correct the excessive deficit and impose deadlines for corrective actions.

Art. 241 The European Union Budget

1. The extent of the European Union Budget shall be determined by law. It shall in all cases include the resources required for the following objectives:
 - (a) The financing of the administration of the European Union Institutions.
 - (b) The financing of the European Union Armed Forces with three per cent of the Gross Domestic Product of each Member State.
 - (c) The repayment of the European Union debt.
 - (d) The financing of the administration of the European Union Agencies.
 - (e) The financing of the European Union Structural Funds.

2. A double-qualified majority of votes shall be necessary for the passing of the European Union Budget in the European Council.

Art. 242 Member State budget

1. Member States have total autonomy in the allocation of their own resources. However, they must follow the European Union guidelines on Borrowing and its Limits (Art. 242) and Apportionment of expenditures (Art. 239).
2. The Member States shall account for the resources paid into the European Union Treasury and include it in their budget.

Art. 243 Borrowing and its Limits

1. Member states are expected to keep their public debt-to-GDP ratio below 60%. If a country's debt level exceeds this threshold, it is expected to make progress towards reaching the 60% target.
2. The European Union shall keep its public debt-to-GDP ratio below 20%. It shall borrow money only in the event of a crisis or when immediate structural investment is necessary.

Art. 244 Financial Equalisation

1. The European Union shall set up Structural Funds with the aim of reducing regional disparities in income, wealth and opportunities, supporting Member States in need of financial assistance and initiating and supporting welfare and reforms throughout the European Union.
2. The European Union shall legislate on the extent and details of such funds.

The Institutions of the European Union

Art. 245 European Union Armed Forces

1. The European Union Armed Forces shall adhere to the Constitution of the European Union and shall defend it against unconstitutional alteration.
2. It shall be the duty of the European Union Armed Forces to defend the territorial integrity of the European Union and its Member States, to serve the European people, to fulfil military responsibilities and to protect the vital interests of the European Union and its Member States.
3. It shall be the obligation of the European Union Armed Forces to protect each Member State equally.
4. The Commissioner of Defence shall be the Commander in Chief of the European Union Armed Forces in peacetime, in wartime this role shall fall on the President of the European Union.
5. The European Union Armed Forces shall be provided with the necessary means to fulfil their obligations. These include fair compensation for their employees and supply of the required weapons and infrastructure.
6. The European Union Armed Forces shall be financed jointly by the Member States to the extent as provided for by the European Congress. This must be at least three per cent of the European Union's Gross Domestic Product.
7. The European Congress shall legislate on the organisation and functioning of the European Union Armed Forces.

Art. 246 Europol

1. Europol shall be the federal law enforcement agency of the European Union. It shall assist the Member States in maintaining law and public order in the European Union. It shall investigate Inter-Member State crime.
2. Europol shall operate under the jurisdiction of the Office of Interior.
3. Europol shall uphold and defend the Constitution of the European Union. It shall follow the laws and principles of the European Union.

4. The European Congress shall legislate on the organisation, financing and functioning of Europol.

Art. 247 Frontex

1. To defend and patrol the land and sea borders of the European Union the Member States shall establish a common border guard. This border guard shall be Frontex.
2. Frontex shall operate under the jurisdiction of the Office of Interior.
3. The European Congress shall legislate on the organisation, financing and functioning of Frontex.

Art. 248 European Court of Auditors

1. The European Court of Auditors shall conduct audits of all revenue and expenditure of the European Union, including those of European Union Institutions, Offices and Agencies. It shall ensure the legality, regularity, and sound financial management of the European Union finances and report on any irregularities encountered during the process.
2. The European Court of Auditors shall be composed of one national from each Member State of the European Union, ensuring representation from across the European Union. Members of the Court shall be chosen based on their expertise in external audit bodies or qualifications suitable for the office.
3. Members of the Court of Auditors shall serve a renewable term of seven years and shall elect a President from among their members.
4. In the performance of their duties, the Members of the Court of Auditors shall act independently and impartially, serving the European Union's general interest. They shall refrain from seeking or taking instructions from any government or external body and shall not engage in any other occupation during their tenure.
5. The European Court of Auditors shall produce an annual report summarizing its findings, to be forwarded to the European Union's institutions and published for public scrutiny. It may also submit special reports or opinions upon request from other European Union institutions.
6. The European Court of Auditors shall adopt its Rules of Procedure, subject to the approval of the European Council, to govern its internal functioning and decision-making processes.
7. The European Congress shall legislate on further details of the functioning of the European Court of Auditors.

Art. 249 European Public Prosecutor's Office

1. The European Public Prosecutor's Office (EPPO) shall be the independent public prosecution office of the European Union. It shall investigate, prosecute and bring to justice crimes against the financial interests of the European Union. These shall include fraud, money laundering, corruption, and illegal lobbying. To this end, it shall cooperate as necessary with national authorities and institutions. It shall ensure the effective and efficient prosecution of such offences throughout the European Union.
2. The EPPO shall be made up of European delegated prosecutors from each Member State of the European Union, ensuring representation and cooperation throughout the European Union. Delegated prosecutors shall be chosen based on their expertise in criminal law and their suitability for the position.
3. European delegated prosecutors shall serve a term of six years, renewable as necessary. The EPPO shall elect a Chief Prosecutor from among its members to lead its activities and represent its interests.
4. In the performance of their duties, the European delegated prosecutors shall act independently and impartially, serving the interests of the European Union. They shall refrain from seeking or taking instructions from any government or external body, ensuring the integrity and fairness of their investigations and prosecutions.
5. The European delegated prosecutors shall commit to upholding integrity and discretion during and after their term of office, refraining from engaging in any other occupation that may compromise their independence or conflict with their duties.
6. The European Congress shall legislate on the conditions of employment, including salaries, allowances, and pensions, for the Chief Prosecutor and European delegated prosecutors. Additionally, the EPPO's members shall be granted privileges and the immunities necessary for the performance of their duties.
7. The EPPO shall draw up regular reports summarising its investigations and prosecutions, which shall be forwarded to the institutions of the European Union and made public in the interests of transparency and accountability.
8. The EPPO shall adopt its Rules of Procedure to govern its internal functioning and decision-making processes, ensuring consistency and fairness in its activities, such rules shall be subject to the approval of the European Council.
9. The European Congress shall legislate on further details of the functioning of the EPPO.

Art. 250 European Intelligence Agency

1. Realizing the necessity of information and intelligence for the security of a state the European Union shall establish the European Intelligence Agency.
2. The European Intelligence Agency shall collect data for the purpose of security of the European Union.
3. The European Intelligence Agency shall not gather the data of European citizens, nor gather information within the territory of the European Union.
4. The Commissioner of Intelligence shall be the head of the European Intelligence Agency.
5. The European Congress shall legislate on the organisation, financing and functioning of the European Intelligence Agency.

Art. 251 European Central Bank

1. The European Central Bank, together with the national central banks, shall constitute the European System of Central Banks (ESCB). The European Central Bank, together with the national central banks of the Member States whose currency shall be the euro, which constitutes the Eurosystem, shall conduct the monetary policy of the Union.
2. The ESCB shall be governed by the decision-making bodies of the European Central Bank. The primary objective of the ESCB shall be to maintain price stability. Without prejudice to that objective, it shall support the general economic policies in the Union to contribute to the achievement of the latter's objectives.
3. The European Central Bank shall have a legal personality. It alone may authorise the issue of the euro. It shall be independent in the exercise of its powers and the management of its finances. European Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies and the governments of the Member States shall respect that independence.
4. The European Central Bank shall adopt such measures as are necessary to carry out its tasks set out in this Constitution and European Union and European Union law. It shall follow the conditions laid down in the Statute of the ESCB and of the European Central Bank.
5. The European Congress shall legislate on the organisation, financing and functioning of the European Central Bank.

Art. 252 European Competition Office

1. The European Competition Office shall make sure that no business or enterprise creates Cartels or Monopolies that lead to less choice and higher prices. It shall make sure that competition between businesses and enterprises is fair. It shall aim to limit anti-competitive conduct.
2. The European Competition Office shall execute the European competition measures.
3. The European Competition Office shall operate under the jurisdiction of the Office of Justice.
4. The European Congress shall legislate on the organisation, financing and functioning of the European Competition Office.

Art. 253 European Patent Office

1. The European Patent Office shall oversee the examination of patent applications to ensure that they meet the legal standards of novelty, utility and non-obviousness. Its primary function shall be to determine the eligibility of inventions for patent protection by ensuring that they meet the criteria set forth in European Union law.
2. In addition, the European Patent Office shall maintain a comprehensive database of granted patents and pending applications to facilitate access to information essential to innovation and technological progress.
3. In carrying out its functions, the European Patent Office shall provide guidance and assistance to inventors and applicants and promote a fair and transparent patent system that encourages creativity and economic development for the benefit of society.
4. The European Congress shall legislate on the organisation, financing and functioning of the European Patent Office.

Art. 254 European Interpreter Office

1. The European Interpreter Office shall ensure all European Union laws, bills, debates, hearings, conferences and trials are translated into all the official languages of the European Union. It ensures that no citizen or institution of the European Union faces problems or disadvantages in understanding official documents in another language of the European Union.
2. The European Congress shall legislate on the organisation, financing and functioning of the European Interpreter Office.

Art. 255 European Election Office

1. The European Election Office shall aim to ensure that all elections in the European Union and its Member States are conducted following the Right to vote and the Right to stand as a candidate in elections. It shall ensure that the principles of personal and equal, free and secret vote are upheld in all elections. To this end, it may oversee the organization and procedure of the elections.
2. The European Congress shall legislate on the organisation, financing and functioning of the European Election Office.

Art. 256 European Information Office

1. The European Information Office shall provide citizens and organisations with the information they need to conduct their business; it shall make sure that European Union law is widely understood.
2. The European Congress shall legislate on the organisation, financing and functioning of the European Information Office.

The Agencies of the European Union

Art. 257 Agencies

1. The European Union and the Member States shall establish Agencies to accomplish specific tasks.
2. Agencies shall have their legal personality and they shall be independent from the Institutions of the European Union.
3. All Agencies shall have specific tasks assigned to them. For instance, encouraging research or opening a dialogue between different interest groups.
4. Agencies of the European Union shall be decentralized.
5. European Agencies may operate on an international level.

Non-Governmental Organisations

Art. 258 Non-Governmental Organisations

1. The European Union shall encourage, support and create a legal basis for the creation of Non-Governmental Organisations.
2. Non-Governmental Organisations shall be independent of governments, non-profit or voluntary groups with their own administration that address or solve issues in support of the public good.
3. The European Union may make donations to Non-Governmental Organisations to support their activities.
4. Non-Governmental Organisations may be local, national or international. No differentiation shall be made between them based on their origin.

Citizens Assemblies

Art. 259 Citizens Assemblies

1. To promote a more inclusive and participatory form of governance, the European Union shall establish a legal framework for Citizens' Assemblies. These assemblies shall serve as a supplementary mechanism for democratic deliberation on specific issues, recognising the importance of diverse and informed perspectives in the decision-making process.
2. The members of Citizens' Assemblies shall be randomly selected from the population of the European Union to ensure a representative depiction of Member States and demographics, including age, gender, socioeconomic status, ethnicity, and educational background.
3. The assembly members shall discuss issues of societal importance, as identified by the European Congress or through public petition.
4. Participants shall engage in informed discussions moderated by trained experts, receiving comprehensive information and materials on the topics under consideration. Deliberations shall be conducted transparently, with proceedings open to the public, ensuring accountability and fostering trust in the democratic process.
5. Citizens' Assemblies shall provide non-binding recommendations based on the collective input and deliberation of the participants. Policymakers within the European Congress shall consider these recommendations in the decision-making process, thereby incorporating the insights of a diverse and representative group of citizens into their legislation.
6. Citizens' Assemblies shall be independent to ensure credibility and avoid undue influence. While maintaining independence, Citizens' Assemblies may collaborate with the European Congress to facilitate the integration of their recommendations into the broader policy-making framework.

Public Wealth and Public Procurement

Art. 260 Handling of Public Wealth

1. Public Wealth shall include all assets and resources that are collectively held by the people. They shall be managed and overseen by the government for the benefit of the people.
2. Public wealth shall be regularly accounted for in detail. When reinvested according to law the Constitution of the European Union and European Union laws regulating Public Procurement shall apply, aiming to achieve transparency and oversight.
3. Public Wealth shall be protected against misuse. To this end data about Public Wealth shall be openly accessible, helping independent and regular audits.
4. Future generations are also entitled to Public Wealth, for this reason, Public Wealth shall be regularly maintained and reinvested.

Art. 261 Public Procurement

1. Public procurement shall be conducted in a fair, competitive, and transparent manner. It shall, in all instances, serve the interest of the public.
2. The primary objective of public procurement shall be to obtain the best value for money, considering factors such as price, quality, sustainability, and fitness for purpose.
3. Public institutions shall use competitive bidding processes for all procurement activities, with exceptions only in limited circumstances and such circumstances shall be clearly defined by law.
4. Public institutions shall provide equal treatment to all potential suppliers and shall not discriminate based on nationality, size, or any other characteristic. They may however give preference to European Union firms.
5. Public institutions shall ensure that procurement contracts are awarded to the bidder whose offer is evaluated as the most advantageous in terms of the established criteria.
6. The European Congress shall further legislate on the Public Procurement.

Lobbying and Corruption

Art. 262 Lobbying

1. Wishing to achieve open and accountable governance, the European Union shall establish and maintain a transparent and regulated framework for lobbying activities that seek to influence European Union policies. Lobbying shall be defined as all activities, whether direct or indirect, undertaken to impact the formulation or implementation of policy and decision-making processes of European Union institutions. The European Union shall institute a mandatory Transparency Register, encompassing individuals, organisations, and entities engaged in lobbying, with clear criteria for registration and penalties for non-compliance. Standardised criteria for recording meetings between lobbyists and European Union officials shall be mandated, ensuring consistency in documentation. Furthermore, a harmonised set of lobbying rules shall be applied uniformly across all European institutions, eliminating exemptions, and disclosure requirements shall extend to include all lobbying interactions involving European Union officials and representatives of foreign governments or entities, with accessible and regularly updated public databases for publication. Individuals who report illegal or unethical activities shall be protected, thereby promoting transparency in European Union policy-making.
2. The European Union shall further legislate on lobbying.

Art. 263 Corruption

1. The European Union recognises corruption as one of the most harmful crimes in our society. Therefore the European Union declares dishonesty, undertaken by a person or an organization entrusted in a position of authority, with the aim of securing personal gain, a crime.
2. All forms of corruption; Petty corruption, Grand corruption and Systemic corruption undermine social trust and must therefore be averted.
3. The European Union shall make sure that the conduct of people of authority shall be recorded and transparent.
4. The European Union shall ensure that there is an easy, well functioning and anonymous way of reporting corruption.
5. The European Union realising that corruption occurs if the corrupt gain is greater than the penalty multiplied by the likelihood of being caught and prosecuted shall make sure that both the penalty and likelihood of being caught and prosecuted are sufficient to avert corruption.

6. The European Union shall take further measures to tackle corruption and fraud.

Civil disobedience, Right of resistance and Independence of Thought

Art. 264 Civil disobedience

1. The European Union recognises the right of all people to conduct civil disobedience without getting punished for their actions, as long as they do not violate the rights of others. Additionally, civil disobedience may in no case; damage property or be violent; and must be morally and ethically justified. If civil disobedience is unjustified the people conducting it may be punished in accordance with their offences.

Art. 265 The Right of Resistance

1. All Europeans shall have the right and obligation to resist any person seeking to abolish this constitutional order if no other remedy is available.

Art. 266 Independence of Thought

1. Every person shall have the duty and the right to think for themselves and to form their own opinions based on their judgement and conscience.
2. People shall be encouraged to develop their own independent and informed views.
3. People shall be responsible for the consequences of their actions, including those resulting from following the directives or instructions of others. People shall not be relieved of such responsibility by claiming the influence of others or external factors, including their superiors or employers. People shall be encouraged to question and critically evaluate the directives and instructions of their superiors, and to act following their judgment and conscience while respecting the rights and interests of others.

The aversion of autocratic interference

Art. 267 The aversion of autocratic interference

1. The European Congress shall identify and label countries that fail to uphold the fundamental principles of human rights, the rule of law, or democracy as autocratic regimes. Such identification shall be based on comprehensive assessments of the respective country's governance, adherence to democratic values, respect for human rights and influence on the domestic affairs of the European Union.
2. Countries labelled as autocratic regimes by the European Congress may face diplomatic and economic sanctions. Such sanctions may include trade restrictions, diplomatic measures, and other actions aimed at discouraging and penalising autocratic interference in the domestic affairs of the European Union.
3. The European Union and its Member States shall collaborate to enhance election security and protect the integrity of democratic processes against foreign and especially autocratic interference.
4. Political parties, media conglomerates, and non-governmental organisations operating within the jurisdiction of the European Union shall undergo immediate scrutiny if they are found to have knowingly accepted financial support originating from countries labelled as autocratic. If such financial support is confirmed, the affected political party, media conglomerate or non-governmental organisation shall face dissolution and prohibition from further operation within the European Union.
5. The European Union shall identify and counteract foreign propaganda and disinformation campaigns that aim to influence public opinion within the European Union. Media outlets found to be involved in disseminating such propaganda shall face penalties, and measures shall be taken to mitigate the impact of misinformation on public discourse.
6. The European Union to strengthen the resilience of the democratic system and preserve the independence of domestic policymaking from undue foreign influence shall regulate foreign lobbying activities. Lobby groups backed financially or acting on behalf of autocratic regimes and foreign states, shall be subject to strict regulations requiring transparent disclosure of their funding sources and activities. They shall be prohibited from directly or indirectly participating in political campaigns, influencing legislative decisions, or advocating policies undermining democratic values. Furthermore, the European Union retains the right to scrutinise and restrict the activities of lobby groups promoting the interests of autocratic states, safeguarding democratic principles and national sovereignty.
7. The European Union and its Member States shall monitor and counter foreign intelligence activities that pose a threat to the domestic affairs of the European Union. Such efforts

shall include cybersecurity and information warfare regulations, continually developed and strengthened to protect against digital threats and manipulative actions by autocratic entities seeking to interfere in the democratic processes of the European Union.

8. The European Congress shall further legislate on autocratic interference in its domestic affairs.

Constitutional amendments

Art. 268 Amendment process of the Constitution of the European Union

1. An amendment to the Constitution of the European Union may be introduced by a Member of the European Parliament or by the people directly proposing a Bill of Amendment drawn up in sections and signed by at least five million voters.
2. The Bill of Amendment introduced to the European Congress shall, in both Houses, under their Rules of procedure, be scrutinised by a Committee and then by the whole House, which shall consider it section by section, after which both Houses may propose with Amendments on the Bill of Amendment. When the Bill is finalised it must be put to a final vote in both Houses.
3. A Bill shall only pass the final vote if it is supported by two-thirds of all the Members of the European Parliament and by a double-qualified majority of all Representatives of the European Council.
4. If the Bill of amendment passes the European Congress it shall then be scrutinised by the Legislature of the Member States. If the Legislature of four-fifths of the Member States approves the Bill of amendment then the Bill of amendment passes the Legislatures of the Member States.
5. A general referendum may be held to repeal, in whole or in part, a Bill of amendment, when so requested by five million voters or the Legislature of ten Member States. Any citizen entitled to vote for the European Parliament has the right to vote in the referendum. The referendum shall be considered to have been carried out if the majority of those eligible have voted and a majority of valid votes have been achieved.
6. If the Bill of Amendment passes the Legislature of the Member States it shall be presented to the Constitutional Court of the European Union. The Constitutional Court of the European Union shall then debate the Bill of Amendment. It shall make sure that no Non-amendable part of the Constitution of the European Union is amended in the Bill of Amendment. Finally, the Constitutional Court of the European Union shall pass a verdict. If they support the Bill of Amendment then it shall become an Amendment to the Constitution of the European Union. If they do not support the Bill of Amendment it shall be returned to the European Congress with the objections written on it. At this point, the Bill of Amendment shall again go through the process of Amendment.
7. No Bill of amendment shall become an Amendment of the Constitution of the European Union without going through the whole Amendment process.

Art. 269 Non-amendable parts of the Constitution of the European Union

1. The republican and democratic form of government shall not be the object of any amendment.
2. The Rule of Law shall not be the object of any amendment.
3. No amendment may be made that limits the extent of the freedom of expression (Article 13), the freedom of the press (Article 13), the freedom of teaching (Article 14), the freedom of assembly (Article 16), the freedom of association (Article 18), the privacy of correspondence, posts and telecommunications (Article 23), the rights of property (Article 26) or the right of asylum (Article 28).
4. No amendment shall be made that limits the equality of European Union citizens (Article 32).
5. No amendment shall be made that does not recognise the Basic Rights of the European Union (all Articles from Article 7 to Article 72).
6. No amendment shall be made that limits the right of resistance (Article 264) or the Independence of thought (Article 265).
7. No amendment shall be made that infringes the separation of the branches of power of the European Union (Legislative powers, Executive powers, Judicial powers, Media powers and Educating powers).
8. No amendment shall be made that differentiates among Member States of the European Union.
9. No amendment shall be made that deprives a Member State, without its consent, of its equal Suffrage in the European Council.
10. No amendment procedure shall be commenced or continued where the integrity of the European Union territory is placed in jeopardy.
11. No amendment shall be made that terminates the Non-amendable parts of the Constitution of the European Union (Article 268).

Final Provisions, Ratification and Signatories

Final Provisions

The principle of Decentralization

1. The European Union, not wishing to create a capital of the European Union or to strengthen one Member State over another, and wishing to strengthen the independence of the institutions of the European Union, recognizing that decentralization promotes greater autonomy and participation of all individuals, shall ensure that its institutions and agencies are not concentrated in a single Member State or a single city, but are distributed throughout the Union.
2. The President of the European Union and his office and the European Commission and its offices shall be located in Brussels, Belgium.
3. The Joint sessions of the European Congress shall be held in Brussels, Belgium.
4. The European Parliament and its offices shall be located in Strasbourg, France; however, it shall also maintain offices in Brussels, Belgium and Luxembourg City, Luxembourg.
5. The European Council and its offices shall be located in Brussels, Belgium.
6. The European Court of Justice and the General Court of the European Union shall have their seats in Luxembourg City, Luxembourg.
7. The European Central Bank shall have its seat in Frankfurt am Main, Germany.
8. The headquarters of the European Armed Forces shall be in
9. The European Court of Auditors shall have its seat in Luxembourg City, Luxembourg.
10. The European Public Prosecutor's Office shall maintain its offices in Luxembourg City, Luxembourg.
11. Frontex shall be based in Warsaw, Poland.
12. Europol shall be based in The Hague, Netherlands.
13. The European Congress shall legislate on the seat of all other Institutions and Agencies, taking into account the principle of decentralization.

The former Treaties

- 1.
- 2.

Ratification

1. The Constitution will be ratified in each Member State under its ratification procedures. Each Member State shall have one year in which to do so.
2. Once the Constitution has received eighteen ratifications, it shall be deemed to have been ratified in those Member States and the first steps may be taken to implement the laws of the Union following the provisions of the Constitution; however, Member States shall not discriminate against Member States where the ratification process is still in progress and shall, if necessary, wait one year until all members have either ratified or rejected this Constitution.
3. At the end of this period, they shall begin to implement the provisions and laws laid down in the Constitution.
4. Laws and Regulations of the former European Union not contrary to this Constitution shall be
- 5.

Drafted and Signatories

1. Drafted and proposed by Nándor Györffy a citizen of the Member State of Hungary in the interest of the whole of Europe.
2. Drafted:
Europe, Hungary, Budapest
Europe, Germany, Constance
Europe, France, Strasbourg
3. Last Modified:
2026 May 5.
4. Made public:
Europe, Belgium, Brussels
5. Signed:
Nándor Györffy

Constance, Germany, 2026 May 9.

The Republic of Austria

1. THE FEDERAL PRESIDENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF AUSTRIA:
2. Federal Chancellor:
3. Federal Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Kingdom of Belgium

1. HIS MAJESTY THE KING OF THE BELGIANS:
2. Prime Minister:

3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Republic of Bulgaria

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF BULGARIA:
2. Prime Minister:
3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Republic of Croatia

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF CROATIA:
2. Prime Minister:
3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Republic of Cyprus

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF CYPRUS:
2. Prime Minister:
3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Czech Republic

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE CZECH REPUBLIC:
2. Prime Minister:

3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Kingdom of Denmark

1. HER MAJESTY THE QUEEN OF DENMARK:
2. Prime Minister:
3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Republic of Estonia

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF ESTONIA:
2. Prime Minister:
3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Republic of Finland

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF FINLAND:
2. Prime Minister:
3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The French Republic

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE FRENCH REPUBLIC:
2. Prime Minister:

3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Federal Republic of Germany

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE FEDERAL REPUBLIC OF GERMANY:
2. Federal Chancellor:
3. Federal Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Hellenic Republic

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE HELLENIC REPUBLIC:
2. Prime Minister:
3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

Hungary

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE REPUBLIC:
2. Prime Minister:
3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Republic of Ireland

1. THE PRESIDENT OF IRELAND:
2. Taoiseach (Prime Minister):

3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Italian Republic

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE ITALIAN REPUBLIC:
2. Prime Minister:
3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Republic of Latvia

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF LATVIA:
2. Prime Minister:
3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Republic of Lithuania

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF LITHUANIA:
2. Prime Minister:
3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Grand Duchy of Luxembourg

1. HIS ROYAL HIGHNESS THE GRAND DUKE OF LUXEMBOURG:
2. Prime Minister:

3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Republic of Malta

1. THE PRESIDENT OF MALTA:

2. Prime Minister:

3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Kingdom of the Netherlands

1. HER MAJESTY THE QUEEN OF THE NETHERLANDS:

2. Prime Minister:

3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Republic of Poland

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF POLAND:

2. Prime Minister:

3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Portuguese Republic

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE PORTUGUESE REPUBLIC:

2. Prime Minister:

3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

Romania

1. THE PRESIDENT OF ROMANIA:

2. Prime Minister:

3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Slovak Republic

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE SLOVAK REPUBLIC:

2. Prime Minister:

3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Republic of Slovenia

1. THE PRESIDENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF SLOVENIA:

2. President of the Government:

3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Kingdom of Spain

1. HIS MAJESTY THE KING OF SPAIN:

2. President of the Government:

3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

The Kingdom of Sweden

1. HIS MAJESTY THE KING OF SWEDEN:

2. Prime Minister:

3. Minister for Foreign Affairs:

